

Rational design of mixed-matrix metal-organic framework membranes for molecular separations

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Conventional separation technologies to separate valuable commodities are energy-intensive, consuming 15% of the worldwide energy. Mixed-matrix membranes, combining processable polymers and selective adsorbents, offer potential to deploy adsorbent distinct separation properties into processable matrix. We report a rational design and construction of highly-efficient mixed-matrix metal-organic framework membrane based on three interlocked criteria: i) fluorinated metal-organic framework, ALFFIVE-1-Ni as molecular sieve adsorbent that selectively enhanced H₂S and CO₂ diffusion while excluding CH₄. ii) Tailoring crystal morphology into nanosheets with maximally exposed (001)-facets. iii) In-plane alignment of (001)-nanosheets in polymer matrix and attainment of [001]-oriented membrane. The membrane demonstrated exceptionally high H₂S and CO₂ separation from natural gas under practical working conditions. This approach offers great potential to translate other key adsorbents into processable matrix.

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Chemical separations are highly energy-intensive and account for around half of the global industrial energy consumption (1, 2). Membrane-based separation can provide an energy-efficient alternative to traditional separation processes like cryogenic distillation and adsorptive separation. Polymer membranes intrinsically undergo a trade-off between the permeability (productivity) and selectivity (efficiency), known as Robeson's upper bound (3, 4). Mixed-matrix membranes (MMMs), combining the distinct properties of selective adsorbents (molecular separation and facilitated gas transport) and polymers (processability and mechanical stability), may enable energy-efficient and environmentally sustainable technologies (5-7). Nevertheless, successful translation of adsorbent distinct properties into MMMs remains a persistent challenge, due to recurring agglomeration and sedimentation of adsorbent fillers in the polymer matrix and incompatibility between adsorbent-polymer interfaces. As a result of these challenges, the attainment of highly selective membranes is hampered as well as the mechanical properties of the membranes are lessened (8).

Various MMMs have been reported, using isotropic or near-anisotropic fillers (6, 7, 9), and these membranes exhibited moderate improvement in selectivity and/or permeability (7, 10, 11). The impact of filler particle size (12), morphology (6, 13), functionality (14), and surface modification (15) in MMMs on gas separation are well documented. An anisotropic morphology, like high-aspect-ratio nanosheets, was recognized to offer several advantages over isotropic fillers. The relatively large external surface area proffers an enhancement of the nanosheets-polymer interface compatibility, permitting high filler loading, while the combination of very short gas diffusion pathways with preserved molecular discrimination may result in a considerable increase of both permeability and selectivity (16).

Only a limited number of metal-organic framework (MOF) nanosheets have been explored in MMMs for gas separation (17-22). Cu-BDC nanosheets (from 2D layer-structured MOF) was first embedded in Matrimid polymer in a form of MMM for CO₂/CH₄ separation (17). The membrane showed moderate selectivity improvement at the expense of a lower CO₂ permeability, plausibly due to none-selective nor promoted transport of CO₂ versus CH₄ in the relatively larger pore system (~6.5 Å). NH₂-MIL-53(A1), a 3D periodic framework with a relatively strong CO₂ interactions, was prepared as nanosheets using CTAB surfactant (18)). Unfortunately, the resultant MMM showed a relatively moderate CO₂/CH₄ separation, plausibly due to residual CTAB on the surface of nanosheets affecting the gas separation properties of the pristine material, pinpointing to the importance of surfactant-free nanosheets preparation. Methods to use contracted pore and/or better performing MOF structures as defect-free nanosheets is of prime importance, as numerous contracted pore MOF structures offer desirable adsorption and molecular diffusion properties

(23) but they are not ideal for conventional exfoliation methods (24). In addition to the attainment of high-aspect-ratio nanosheets of desired MOFs, it is essential to develop suitable strategies that can afford requisite alignment of nanosheets within the polymer matrix.

We report a concept for the construction of a mixed-matrix metal-organic framework (MMMOF) membrane based on three interlocked criteria: i) a MOF filler possesses optimal pore size and shape, functionality, host-guest interaction that selectively enhanced H₂S and CO₂ diffusion while excluding CH₄. ii) Tailoring MOF crystal morphology along 001 crystallographic direction into high-aspect-ratio (001)-nanosheets that proffers maximum exposure of one-dimensional (1D) channel and promotes nanosheets-polymer interaction resultant high nanosheets loading. iii) In-plane (face-to-face) alignment of (001)-nanosheets in polymer matrix with proximal distance to translate the molecular separation properties of single nanosheets into a uniformly [001]-oriented macroscopic MMMOF membrane.

Hydrolytically stable fluorinated AIFFFIVE-1-Ni (KAUST-8), when used as an adsorbent, showed excellent separation properties for H₂S/CH₄ and CO₂/CH₄ (25, 26). This MOF possesses appropriate H₂S and CO₂ adsorption and separation properties, high chemical stability towards H₂S that instigate AIFFFIVE-1-Ni as a potential molecular sieve filler in MMMOF membrane for natural gas upgrading. However, effective deployment of AIFFFIVE-1-Ni (a 3-periodic MOF with 1D channels) as a filler into membranes, requires its morphology to be tailored into nanosheets with defined crystallographic direction, for maximum surface exposure of 1D channels (25, 26).

The structure of AIFFFIVE-1-Ni along the [110] or [1-10] direction is shown in Fig. 1A. The 2-periodic square-grid layer constructed by linking Ni(II) with pyrazine ligand are pillared by [AlF₅(H₂O)]²⁻ anions in the third dimension to construct a 3-periodic framework/structure with the primitive cubic (pcu) underlying topology and pore walls comprised of [AlF₅(H₂O)]²⁻ anions, prohibiting access to the pore system in [110] and [1-10] direction (Fig. 1A). Schematic illustrations of a typical truncated-bipyramidal morphology of the crystal and its channel orientation are shown in Fig. 1B. The structure consists of 1D ultra-small channels (represented in green) that run along the [001] direction (Fig. 1, B and C). These channels are accessible to only relatively small gas molecules (*e.g.* He, H₂, CO₂, O₂, H₂S, N₂ etc.).

Synthesis and characterization of MOF nanosheets

A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of AIFFFIVE-1-Ni crystals obtained by conventional hydrothermal synthesis, suggesting the material is not suitable for membrane fabrication (fig. S1). Grinding large particles into nanoparticles may not improve their gas separation performances as the majority of the nanoparticles may expose the non-accessible (110) and (1-10) facets. The 1D channels of

AlFFIVE-1-Ni can only be fully exploited if the morphology is controlled into nanosheets with completely exposed (001) facets. Therefore, the crystallographic growth along *c*-direction must be significantly reduced or completely suppressed relative to the desired growth along *a*- and *b*-directions. We develop a bottom-up synthesis approach yielding high-aspect-ratio nanosheets. Performing the synthesis under a reduced $[\text{AlF}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2-}$ pillaring units concentration along with decreasing synthesis temperature promoted the formation of crystals with large lateral dimensions and prevented the growth in the *c*-direction (Fig. 1A, see supplementary materials and figs. S1 and S2). Further, the addition of ethanol into the reaction mixture was found to be very effective to further reduce crystal thickness while maintaining the nanosheets morphology (fig. S3).

Diverse MOF nanosheets have been prepared either from 2D layer-structured MOFs by exfoliation methods (27) or from 3D periodic framework by 2D oxide sacrifice approach (28) and/or surfactant-assisted synthesis (18, 29). We present a bottom-up synthesis method for the preparation of MOF nanosheet from a 3D periodic fluorinated MOF with contracted pore system (25). Importantly, we did not use surfactant, modulator, or template, and synthesis was accomplished at relatively low temperature (55 °C) resultant nanosheets are defect-free (STEM analyses) and undesirable substance-free, the essential requirements for membrane application. The optimized synthesis method differs from the bulk synthesis (25) and is scalable (fig. S4).

Adjusting the synthesis conditions afforded the crystal morphology control from aggregated truncated bipyramidal morphology to nanosheets (Fig. 1D and figs. S1 to S3). SEM images reveal that synthesized square-shaped nanosheets exhibit an average lateral dimension of 0.5-4 μm and thickness in the range of 20-50 nm, resulting in an aspect ratio greater than 25 (Fig. 1D). A scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) image of nanosheets (Fig. 1E) corroborates the higher aspect ratio. The nanosheets dispersion is supported by the observed Tyndall effect using a green laser (Fig. 1E, inset, and Movie S1). Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern of the material (Fig. 1G), shows preferred orientation effect of (001)-nanosheets with the $00l$ ($l=2n$) reflections significantly enhanced, further confirming the successful synthesis of nanosheets with AlFFIVE-1-Ni structure.

In addition, we developed a synthesis method to produce nanoparticles (Fig. 1F). SEM images reveal that nanoparticles are fairly uniform with particle size *ca.* 50-120 nm and PXRD confirmed AlFFIVE-1-Ni structure (Fig. 1G). The CO₂ sorption isotherms affirm that bulk material, nanosheets and nanoparticles exhibit similar CO₂ uptake capacity (fig. S5). Variable temperature CO₂ adsorption isotherms on

nanosheets are shown (Fig. 1H). The versatility and scope of our MOF nanosheets synthetic strategy was further evaluated with the fabrication of the FeFFIVE-1-Ni (KAUST-9) nanosheets (fig. S6) (25).

Atomic structure analysis of MOF nanosheets

Annular Bright-Field (ABF) images taken with the C_s -corrected STEM from the nanosheet along the [001] and the [100] directions were shown in Fig 2, A and D, respectively. The images offer an unambiguous visualization of the atomic structure, and the corresponding Fourier Diffraction (FD), and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern were inserted at the top right in the images with indices based on the space group $I4/mcm$ with $a=9.86 \text{ \AA}$ and $c=15.25 \text{ \AA}$. The image resolution was confirmed to be 1.6 \AA by 0-60 reflection marked by a red circle in the FD of Fig 2A, and was among the highest spatial resolution ever achieved for any MOFs. This observation (and figs. S7 and S8) corroborates the preferential crystal orientation, (001)-AIFFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets. Symmetry averaged image of Fig 2A with $p4mmm$ improved signal-to-noise ratio greatly and specified the atoms (Fig. 2B). Strong dark spots were observed with separation of $\approx 6.91 \text{ \AA}$, consistent with the distance between adjacent inorganic extended chains (columns) formed by $--F-Ni-F-Al-F--$ (Fig. 2 C). Additionally, two weak dark elongated signals were also observed between the strong dark spots (separated by $\approx 1.9 \text{ \AA}$), which can be attributed to a part of pyrazine, 2 carbon and 1 nitrogen atoms, acting as a linker between adjacent Ni(II).

Overcoming a big difficulty induced by the preferred orientation of nanosheets along the [001], high-resolution ABF images were taken with the [100] incidence, which is perpendicular to the [001] direction (Fig. 2D and fig. S9). Fig. 2D visualizes the square grid of Ni(II) and pyrazine pillared by $[AlF_5(H_2O)]^{2-}$, where the dark contrast is associated with Ni(II). The crystal structure of AIFFFIVE-1-Ni along [100] direction matches well the corresponding experimental ABF image (Fig. 2E, and fig. S9). This in-depth STEM study confirms the successful synthesis of (001)-AIFFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets (hereafter as (001)-AIFFFIVE or (001)-nanosheets) with excellent crystallinity and maximum exposure of 1D channels (Fig. 2F), which is a highly desirable morphology for achieving in-plane alignment of nanosheets in the polymer matrix.

Fabrication of [001]-oriented MMMOF membrane

It is of prime importance to in-plane align (001)-nanosheets in a polymer matrix to fabricate a uniform [001]-oriented/c-oriented MMMOF membrane and translate the 1D channel alignment from single nanosheets into a macroscopic continuous membrane for an efficient molecular separation (Fig. 3A). Commercially available state-of-the-art polyimide 6FDA-DAM, and lab synthesized 6FDA-DAM-DAT (1:1) and 6FDA-DAT polyimides were chosen as polymer matrices owing to their high thermal and

chemical stabilities, good mechanical strength, and excellent processability. We examined three different solvents (CHCl_3 , THF, and DCM) as dispersant mediums to evaluate the effect of solvents for membrane fabrication and resultant CO_2/CH_4 separation. A solution-casting method was performed to fabricate pure polymeric and MMMOF membranes with a thickness of *ca.* 50–70 μm (supplementary method). The solvents effect in pure polymeric membranes was minimal. However, in MMMOF membrane, CHCl_3 presented higher CO_2/CH_4 selectivity followed by THF and DCM (fig. S10 and S11, and table S1). We evaluated nanosheets' dispersibility in different solvents and allow them to sediment, we noticed nanosheets begin sedimentation after 6~8 h in DCM, 22~25 h in THF, and no sedimentation in CHCl_3 even after 5 days. Thus, higher selectivity can be attributed to the better nanosheets dispersibility that prevents nanosheets sedimentation and/or agglomeration during membrane fabrication resultant homogeneous nanosheets alignment inside the polymer matrix.

The cross-section SEM images of 58.9 wt% nanosheets in 6FDA-DAM [(001)-AIFIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM, parenthesis refer to MOF loading by wt%] reveal a uniform in-plane alignment of nanosheets in the polymer matrix (Fig. 3B and fig. S12). The focused ion beam SEM (FIB-SEM) images on an extensive area evidence that the majority of nanosheets are uniformly and in-plane aligned throughout the membrane (Fig. 3C, fig. S13, and Movie S2). These analyses also reveal an excellent nanosheets-polymer interface compatibility. XRD patterns of associated membrane (Fig. 3D) show only two major Bragg diffractions (indexed as the (002) and (004) crystallographic planes of AIFIVE-1-Ni structure) corroborating the strong preferential in-plane alignment of (001)-nanosheets and the attainment of the desired uniform [001]-oriented MMMOF continuous membrane. These results demonstrate that the successful translation of single (001)-nanosheets into a [001]-oriented macroscopic membrane, where 1D channels of nanosheets are all parallel, an ideal scenario for distinct molecular separation (Fig. 3A).

Shear-flow or shear-force induced preferential alignment of 2D nanosheets within polymer matrix have been reported (17, 30). Here, (001)-nanosheets in-plane (*c*-axis) alignment is induced by a slow evaporation of solvent “slow evaporation-induced in-plane alignment of nanosheets” in the course of the membrane fabrication process. During slow solvent evaporation, nanosheets gradually self-arrange according to the minimum energy configuration (31)). The nanosheets concentration gradient and presence of the liquid-vapor interface may assists as a nucleating surface origins in-plane aligned nanosheets domains to grow gradually inward (Fig. 3E). If the solvent evaporation process is relatively fast, the nanosheets alignment may be kinetically affected and the final alignment may consolidate into a thermodynamically unfavored state (Fig. 3G) (32). In addition, solvent/(nanosheet+polymer) mass ratio

of 22-35 was found to be an optimal range for suitable in-plane alignment. Centrifugal force can also align nanosheets, accordingly [001]-oriented ultrathin membrane on porous α -Al₂O₃ support was prepared by spin coating method.

MOF loading, and associated properties of membranes were additionally analyzed by thermogravimetric analysis, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and XRD (figs. S14 to S16). We attained nanosheets loadings up to 59.9 wt% in 6FDA-DAM-DAT and 60.3 wt% in 6FDA-DAT, importantly, nanosheets loadings (up to 60 wt%) are remarkably high than isotropic fillers loadings (<35 wt%) (10). The ability to increase nanosheets loading offers an opportunity to closely mimic the associated pure MOF membrane, as well as to improve the separation performance of the membranes since the agglomeration, sedimentation, and random orientation of nanosheets within the polymer matrix is circumvented at high loadings. In the present case, no such adverse effects were observed (figs. S17 to S20).

Schematic illustrations of randomly oriented AIFIVE-1-Ni nanoparticles embedded in polymer matrix is shown (Fig. 3H). The cross-section SEM image and XRD patterns of 37.1 wt% nanoparticles in 6FDA-DAM polymer showed a random orientation of the nanoparticles inside polymer matrix (Fig. 3, I and J, and fig. S21). Young's modulus and elongation strain of nanoparticles and nanosheets containing membranes were evaluated (Fig. 3K, and fig. S22). It was found that the incorporation of nanoparticles or nanosheets into polymer matrix results in an enhancement of Young's modulus and this enhancement was substantial in nanosheets containing membranes (Fig. 3K and table S3), which can be attributed to the better compatibility between nanosheets and polymer. Membranes fabricated using nanoparticles maintain good mechanical properties at relatively low MOF loading (26.3 wt%). Nanoparticle loadings up to 37.1 wt% were possible before the membrane became defective or too fragile to handle for gas separation studies. High loading (58.9 wt%) was possible using nanosheets (Fig. 3K, and fig. S22). Nanosheets proffered smooth and extended external surface area compared to nanoparticles, which promoted interactions with the polymer. The optimum nanosheets loading was found up to 64 wt%. Beyond this limit the resultant membrane was difficult to handle for gas separation studies due to its apparent fragility and plausible defects, resulting in relatively high permeability with lower selectivity.

We further endeavored to elucidate the enhanced interaction between nanosheets and polymer. The MOF-polymer suspension was prepared by stirring (250 rpm) at 35 °C for 2 h before membrane casting. We noticed MOF-polymer suspension became viscous and the relative viscosity change of nanosheets-polymer was considerably higher than that of nanoparticle-polymer suspension (Fig. 3L). The higher

viscosity of suspension implies the enhanced nanosheets-polymer interaction, possibly hydrogen bonding interaction between the imide groups of the 6FDA and the H of the pyrazine from (001)-nanosheets is plausibly providing better mechanical properties of nanosheet-incorporated membranes.

The gas separation performances of nanoparticles and (001)-nanosheets containing membranes were assessed under an equimolar CO₂/CH₄ mixture, and compared based on the volume and weight fraction (fig. S23). Regardless, the nanosheet membranes demonstrated substantially better separation. Even at similar MOF loading nanosheets offered higher permeability and selectivity (fig. S23). Nanoparticles always compensate permeability to gain selectivity that can be attributed to random orientation of nanoparticles with non-permeable (110) and (1-10) facets perpendicular to gas diffusion direction (Fig. 3I), ascertaining the importance of (001)-nanosheet morphology.

We also fabricated membrane using (001)-nanosheets in randomly aligned fashion and evaluated CO₂/CH₄ separation (fig. S24). The membrane presented high permeability but significantly reduced selectivity, presumably due to the presence of non-selective gas diffusion path associated to discontinuity of nanosheets staking as revealed by SEM images (Fig. 3G and fig. S24AB). This comparative study corroborates that in-plane alignment is essential to maximize membrane performance (fig. S24C).

We further evaluated how pore size/shape, and host-guest interactions are critical for concurrent enhancement of selectivity and permeability. Accordingly, we selected three MOFs affording their attainment as nanosheets morphology and with different pore system features. Ultra-small pore (~2.1 Å), Zn₂(bim)₄ nanosheets showed a negligible improvement in the selectivity associated with a substantial decrease in permeability. Relatively large pore (~6.2 Å), Zn-TCPP nanosheets showed higher permeability but associated with reduced selectivity (fig. S25). These results are in line with CO₂ adsorption isotherms of associated MOF nanosheets (fig. S25). Only (001)-AIFIVE nanosheets MMMOF demonstrated a significant concurrent enhancement of selectivity and permeability.

The in silico constructed (001)-AIFIVE/polymer composite model is illustrated (Fig. 3M and figs. S27 to 30). The top view reveals that polymer covers 1D channel of (001)-nanosheets (Fig. 3M), forming interlocked perpendicular pore zones. The side view confirms that the polymer remains at the MOF surface, thus no polymer penetration into the pores (fig. S27). We constructed a second nanosheet/6FDA-DAM composite model corresponding to a 42 wt% (001)-nanosheets loading in complement to the pristine one associated with a 59 wt% (001)-nanosheets loading (Fig. S27). The association of two components in the interfacial region is held by means of continued hydrogen bonding interactions with a nanosheets-polymer interface distances that ranges from 2.5 to 6.5 Å for both membranes (Fig. S27C and F). The so-

created interfacial region is characterized by the presence of interconnected pores from 2.5 to 4.0 Å size (fig. S29). This restricted dimension a priori prevents the gas to spread along the direction parallel to the nanosheets surface thus favoring straightforward pathways for the gas through the oriented 1D channel nanosheets/polymer, pinpointing to the importance of uniform [001]-oriented membranes for enhanced separation performance. Grand Canonical Monte Carlo (GCMC) simulations were performed to explore the CO₂ and CH₄ separation properties of the resulting membranes at 298 K. An analysis of the single-component (fig.S31) and binary mixture (Fig. 3N and fig. S31C) adsorption mechanism evidenced that CH₄ is almost exclusively adsorbed in the polymer phase while CO₂ equally populates the pores of the MOF and polymers (Fig.3N and fig. S31), confirming that nanosheets acts as a molecular barrier for CH₄. The interfacial region was found to be accessible to gas molecules, thus ensuring a connecting-path between the polymer and the oriented 1D MOF channel.

The impact of three interlocked criteria on gas separation properties

We conducted single gas permeation on [001]-oriented membranes and associated polymer membranes using 9 different gas molecules (fig. S32 and table S4). [001]-oriented membranes show higher CO₂ permeability as compared to its pure polymer membranes while their CH₄ permeability remain similar (Fig. 4A). This result corroborates a more effective transport of CO₂ via 1D channels of (001)-nanosheets that leads to the enhanced CO₂/CH₄ selectivity. It is a highly looked-for property in a particular MOF filler, allowing its deployment with various polymer matrices for concurrent enhancement of selectivity and permeability (fig. S32 and table S4).

Theoretical CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability of pure (001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni membrane were 354 and 2035 barrer (back-calculated using Maxwell model). Experimentally obtained CO₂ permeability and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity of (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM, (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT, and (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAT membranes at different nanosheets loading are shown (Fig. 4B, and table S5). The in-plane aligned incorporation of nanosheets into the polymer matrix prompted a substantial increase in both CO₂ permeability and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity (Fig. 4B and table S5).

Single and mixed-gas separation studies under different CO₂ feed compositions (CO₂/CH₄: 10/90; 20/80 and 50/50) and feed pressure on [001]-oriented membranes and associated pure polymer membranes are shown (Fig. 4C and fig. S33 to S35). (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM membrane exhibited a higher CO₂/CH₄ selectivity under mixed gas as compared to single gas feeds, in contrast to pure 6FDA-DAM (fig. S33B). Under mixed gas permeation, the preferential adsorption of CO₂ in nanosheets leads to remarkably reduced CH₄ permeability and therefore, enhanced CO₂/CH₄ selectivity (fig. S33D). (001)-

AIFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT and (001)-AIFFIVE/6FDA-DAT membranes presented similar single and mixed gas selectivity (fig. S34D and S35D).

CO₂ concentration-dependent study revealed that mixed gas CO₂ permeability is similar to that of single gas permeability at a relatively high feed CO₂ concentration (CO₂/CH₄:50/50), nevertheless, CO₂ permeability gradually decreased as CO₂ feed concentration decreased to CO₂/CH₄: 20/80 to 10/90 while selectivity was preserved (fig. S33D, S34D and S35D). CO₂ permeability decrease is highly likely due to the higher competition between CH₄ and CO₂. These results imply that CO₂/CH₄ separation at relatively low CO₂ concentration (CO₂/CH₄:20/80 and 10/90, typical CO₂ concentration in natural gas) is challenging but is of practical importance. Even under CO₂/CH₄:10/90 mixture, mixed gas CO₂ permeability improvement of 113% and 110%, and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity enhancement of 144% and 139% were achieved for (001)-AIFFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT and (001)-AIFFIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT membranes, respectively, as compared to associated pure polymer membranes (Fig. 3C, fig. S34 and S35, and Tables S7 and S8). The enhanced separation corroborates the importance of judicious choice of MOF fillers and polymer pairs. These results also demonstrate that the relative enhancement of permeability and selectivity is pronounced in relatively low permeable polymer (table S6-8).

Temperature-dependent (20-100 °C) single and mixed-gas CO₂/CH₄ separation on [001]-oriented membranes and associated pure polymer membranes are shown (Fig. 4D and fig. S36 to S38). Increasing the permeation temperature significantly affects the CO₂/CH₄ separation. Particularly, both selectivity and permeability of pure polymeric membrane and nanoparticle membranes substantially deteriorated (Fig. 3D, fig. S36-S38). In contrast, in [001]-oriented membranes, the CO₂ permeability significantly increases with increasing temperature while retaining selectivity (fig. S36-S38). Likewise, we obtained variable temperature CO₂ adsorption isotherms on (001)-nanosheet powder (Fig. 1H). As the temperature increases the CO₂ adsorption lessens (weaker interactions). This decrease is pronounced for a temperature increase from 75 to 100 °C, prompting a significant enhancement of CO₂ permeability at relatively higher temperatures (Fig. S36-38). Notably, (001)-AIFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane demonstrated a drastic concurrent enhancement in CO₂ permeability of 355 % and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity of 470% compared to the pure 6FDA-DAM-DAT polymer even at 100 °C and under (CO₂/CH₄: 20/80) separation (Fig. 4D and table S9 to S11). This CO₂/CH₄ separation at elevated temperature is the consequence of enhanced CO₂ diffusion via 1D channels of (001)-nanosheets, uniform in-plane alignment of nanosheets and remarkably high nanosheets loading.

We deconvoluted CO₂ and CH₄ permeability into diffusion coefficient (diffusivity, D_i) and sorption coefficient (solubility, S_i) based on the solution-diffusion model (33). By changing permeation temperature membranes exhibited opposite propensity of solubility and diffusivity of the gases (CO₂ and CH₄). Specifically, increasing the temperature considerably decreases CO₂ and CH₄ solubility but substantially increases CO₂ diffusivity in both membranes (fig. S39 A and B). The (001)-AIFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane demonstrated a significant enhancement in CO₂ diffusivity but a sharp decrease in CH₄ diffusivity, compared to 6FDA-DAM-DAT (fig. S39, A and B and table S12), affording a diffusion dominated with exceptionally high CO₂/CH₄ separation in a wide range of temperatures (Fig. 5E, and fig.S39C). We measured membrane stability under thermal stress, (001)-AIFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane demonstrated excellent reversibility in CO₂ permeability and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity in a wide range of temperature and a duration of least 400 h (Fig. 4F).

A comparison of CO₂/CH₄ separation performance of [001]-oriented membranes with other reported MOF-nanoparticles/6FDA-polyimides membranes is presented in Fig. 4G and tables S13 to S15. It is clear from Fig. 5G that the performance of the [001]-oriented membranes reported here exceeds that of others reported in the literature. More appropriate comparison with MOF-nanosheets/polymer membranes attests to the superior performance of [001]-oriented membranes (fig. S40 and table S14) (17, 18, 34, 35). The CO₂/CH₄ separation on ultrathin [001]-oriented membrane on porous α -Al₂O₃ supports was assessed. Preliminary results exhibited an 11 fold increase of CO₂ permeance than thick membrane and selectivity was preserved (fig. S41). Although better separation performances have been reported for thin supported zeolite and carbon molecular sieve membrane films (36), this family of MMMOF membranes have a straightforward manufacture process, excellent mechanical properties and stability to stream, with no signs of plasticization were observed for more than 30 days,

As CO₂/CH₄ separation at relatively low CO₂ concentrations (10%) is more challenging than that of high concentration (50%), the latter concentration is typically analyzed for study purposes (Table S15). Importantly, [001]-oriented membranes demonstrated outstanding separation at relatively low CO₂ concentration. Correspondingly, we dedicated our gas separation to the ternary mixture under realistic row natural gas composition (H₂S/CO₂/CH₄: 1/9/90; 2/18/80 and 5/5/90) (37). For natural gas purification, both CO₂ and H₂S must be removed from CH₄, hence the acid gas removal performance can be evaluated by measuring the total acid gas permeability [$P(\text{CO}_2) + P(\text{H}_2\text{S})$] and selectivity [$P(\text{CO}_2) + P(\text{H}_2\text{S})/P(\text{CH}_4)$](12). Even under H₂S/CO₂/CH₄:1/9/90 mixture, the mixed gas (H₂S + CO₂) permeability improvement of 63%, 104% and 140%, and (H₂S+CO₂)/CH₄ selectivity enhancement of 123%, 112% and

103% were achieved for the (001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM, (001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT and (001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT membranes, respectively, compared to the associated pure polymer membranes (Table S16). AIFVIVE-1-Ni has a similar adsorption selectivity ($\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{CO}_2$ selectivity close to 1), therefore it is capable of removing both gases simultaneously (26). We have demonstrated an adsorbent separation selectivity can be translated into the processable matrix.

The comparative study reveals that the performance of the [001]-oriented membranes reported here exceeds that of others reported in the literature (Fig. 4H) (38, 39). The performance stability of membrane under continuously mixed gas permeation conditions is a critical test to assess the membrane longevity and the reproducibility of its associated properties. Direct application of our best-performing membranes to a 1/9/90: $\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{CO}_2/\text{CH}_4$ mixture leads to 6/85/09: $\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{CO}_2/\text{CH}_4$ mixture in permeate site at least 30 days of continuous operation (fig. S42).

We further evaluated the separation performance of [001]-oriented membranes under high feed pressure that reflects practical natural gas purification (40). Membrane permeation was studied under high feed pressures up to 35 bar (Fig. 4I and fig. S43). Importantly, no abrupt selectivity and/or permeability loss occurred in the [001]-oriented membranes for the total acidic gas removal even under 35 bar pressure (fig. S43 and S44).

The separation performances of oriented membranes were further tested for other gas pairs, including H_2/N_2 , H_2/CH_4 and $\text{H}_2/\text{C}_3\text{H}_8$ and subsequently compared with the literature (3) in fig. S45. The resultant membranes exhibited excellent selectivity and permeability enhancement for these gas pairs, far beyond the upper-bounds for polymeric membranes.

Conclusions

The enhanced performances reported here can be rationalized by recognizing the importance of three essential criteria described earlier. The attainment of in-plane alignment and extremely high loading of (001)-nanosheets is distinctively responsible for the achieved separation performance. Nanosheets selectively transporting gases based on their kinetic diameter through the oriented membranes. In fact, this centimeter-scale flexible [001]-oriented membrane can be regarded as a single piece of a flexible crystal where thousands of nanosheets are uniformly aligned in a predefined crystallographic direction, and the gaps between aligned nanosheets are filled with polymer. The results confirm the potential of tailoring MOF crystal morphology into oriented nanosheets, allowing the desired orientation of the 1D channels parallel to the gas diffusion direction and proffering opportunities to maximize the performance of the oriented membrane as demonstrated here for various gas separations.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

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Materials and Methods

Supplementary Text

Figs. S1 to S47

Tables S1 to S20

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Movies S1 and S2

Fig. 1. Crystal structure and morphology of AIFVIVE-1-Ni (point group $4/mmm$). (A) Structure view along $[110]$ or $[1-10]$ direction. (B) Schematic illustration of truncated bipyramidal morphology and 1D channel orientation. (C) Structure view along the $[001]$ direction. (D) SEM image of nanosheets. Inset: large 001 surface and short channel. (E) Low-resolution STEM image of nanosheets. Inset: photos showing Tyndall effect on nanosheets, using a green laser. (F) SEM image of nanoparticles. Inset: depicted crystal morphology and long channel. (G) Powder XRD patterns ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) of nanosheets and nanoparticles. (H) CO_2 adsorption isotherms of nanosheets between 20 to 100 $^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 2. Cs-corrected STEM images of AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets acquired from different zone axes. (A) An annular bright-field (ABF) image along [001] with the Fourier diffractogram (FD). **(B)** Symmetry averaged image of (A) and an overlaid crystal structure. **(C)** Enlarged a part marked by the dotted red rectangle and intensity profile along the red arrow of (B), and associated structure model. **(D)** ABF image taken with [100] incidence. **(E)** Wiener filtered image with superimposed atomic structure. Color code: Ni(II) orange, Al(III) purple, C gray, F green, N blue. **(F)** Schematic illustration of nanosheet with 1D channel orientation.

Fig. 3. Fabrication and characterization of [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes. (A) Schematic illustration of [001]-oriented membrane and an efficient H₂S and CO₂ separation process through 1D channel. (B and C) Cross-section SEM image (B) and FIB-SEM image (C) of (001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM membrane. (D) XRD patterns of [001]-oriented membrane and nanosheet crystallite. (E) Illustration of 'slow evaporation-induced in-plane alignment' of nanosheets in polymer matrix. (F) Photographs of membrane. (G) Cross-section SEM image of random fashion nanosheets membrane. (H) Illustration of random fashion nanoparticles embedded in polymer matrix. (I and J) Cross-section SEM image (I) and XRD pattern (J) of nanoparticle(37.1)/6FDA-DAM membrane. (K) Mechanical studies of the membranes. (L) Relative viscosity changes of MOF/polymer and polymer suspension. (M and N) Computational studies of [001]-oriented membrane. Color code: polymer phase (transparent sky blue), MOF in (001)-facet (green) and (110)- or (1-10)-facet (purple).

Fig. 4. Gas separation properties. (A) Gas permeability of gases with various kinetic diameters. (B) CO₂ permeability and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity of [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes with various nanosheets loading in wt% and predicted pure (001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni membrane; pure gas permeation (CO₂ at 1 bar and CH₄ at 4 bar, 35 °C). (C and D) Effects of feed CO₂ concentration and temperature on CO₂ permeability and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity for [001]-oriented and pure polymeric membranes, mixed-gas permeation (CO₂/CH₄: 50/50 at 2 bar, 20/80 at 5 bar, and 10/90 at 10 bar, 35 °C) (C) and temperature region between 20 and 100 °C (D). (E) Variation of CO₂/CH₄ sorption and diffusion selectivity with respect to temperature between 20 and 100 °C. (F) Long-term stability and reversibility of CO₂ permeability and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity under thermal stress in (001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane. (G) Plot of CO₂/CH₄ selectivity versus CO₂ permeability providing a recent literature review of polymer/MOF-based MMMs. (H) (H₂S+CO₂)/CH₄ mixed-gas separation properties of [001]-oriented and pure polymer membranes, and comparison with the literature; permeation conditions and individual H₂S and CO₂ permeability and H₂S/CH₄ and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity are listed in Supplementary Table 16. The dash black line indicates the general trade-off between permeability and selectivity in glassy polymers under the described test condition. (I) Permeability and selectivity of [001]-oriented membrane under feed pressures between 5 and 35 bar, at 35 °C. The dash black line in Fig B and G indicates the

Robeson upper bound for state-of-the-art polymer membranes ref (3). The average permeation data are presented; error bars represent the standard error of three membranes ($n = 3$). 1 barrer = 10^{-10} cc(STP) cm cm^{-2} s^{-1} cmHg^{-1} .

Supplementary Materials for

Rational design of mixed-matrix metal organic framework membranes for
molecular separations

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Materials and Methods

Materials

Nickel (II) nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.99%, Aldrich), nickel (II) acetate tetrahydrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{OCOCH}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99%, Organics), iron (III) nitrate nonahydrate ($\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.95%, Aldrich), aluminum (III) nitrate nonahydrate ($\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.99%, Aldrich), aluminum (III) hydroxide hydrate ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Aldrich), pyrazine ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}_2$, 99%, Aldrich), hydrofluoric acid (HF, 48 wt% in H_2O), methylpyridine ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$, 99%, Sigma-Aldrich), acetic anhydride ($(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2\text{O}$, 98%, Sigma-Aldrich), N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{NO}$, 99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich), chloroform (CHCl_3 , 99.8%, Sigma-Aldrich), tetrahydrofuran (THF, 99%, Sigma-Aldrich), dichloromethane (DCM, 99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich), methanol (CH_3OH , 99.9%, VWR), ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$, 99.7%, VWR), were purchased and used.

4,4'-(Hexafluoroisopropylidene)diphthalic anhydride ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_6\text{F}_6\text{O}_6$, 6FDA, 99%, Sigma-Aldrich), diamine 2,4,6-trimethyl-1,3-diaminobenzene ($(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{C}_6\text{H}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, DAM, 96%, Sigma-Aldrich), 2,6-diaminotoluene (DAT) ($\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NH}_2)_2$, DAT, 97%, Sigma-Aldrich) were purchased and purified by sublimation. Polyimide 6FDA-DAM (Mw = 330 kDa, PDI: 2.48) was purchased from Akron Polymer Systems, Inc.

H_2 (99.999%), N_2 (99.999%), CO_2 (99.999%), CH_4 (99.999%), C_3H_6 (99.5%), C_3H_8 (99.5%) and mixed gases consisting of CO_2/CH_4 : 50/50, 20/80, 10/90 and $\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{CO}_2/\text{CH}_4 = 1/9/90$, 2/18/80, 5/5/90 were purchased from Air Liquid and AHG.

Methods

Synthesis of (001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{AlF}_5\text{N}_4\text{NiO}_3$) nanosheets

Pyrazine ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}_2$, 1.80 g, 22.03 mmol) was dissolved in 9 ml of 2:1 (v/v) mixture ethanol- H_2O . Subsequently, nickel acetate tetrahydrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{OCOCH}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.20 g, 8.84 mmol) was added into the above solution and the solution was sonicated for 2 minutes. Separately, aluminum hydroxide ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, 0.32 g, 4.10 mmol) was dissolved in 4 ml of 3:1 (v/v) mixture HF- H_2O . These two solutions were mixed together and sonicated for 3 minutes, a sky blue mixture was formed. The solvothermal reaction was carried out at 50 °C for 3 days under a static condition. The precipitated product was collected by centrifugation at 5000 rpm, and washed with total 300 ml of water, and subsequently washed with 60 ml of ethanol. Finally, nanosheets was dispersed in required amount of CHCl_3 , THF or DCM solution.

(001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets stock solution

To prevent agglomeration, nanosheets was not dried before film casting and formation. Concentrations of nanosheets in CHCl_3 , THF or DCM solution was adjusted to be around 100 mg of MOF/ml solution.

Scale-up synthesis of (001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets

In a typical synthetic procedure, pyrazine (18 g) was dissolved in 90 ml of 2:1 (v/v) mixture ethanol- H_2O . Subsequently, nickel acetate tetrahydrate (22 g) was added into the above solution and the solution was sonicated for 4 minutes. Separately, aluminum hydroxide (3.2 g) was dissolved in 40 ml of 3:1 (v/v) mixture HF- H_2O . These two solutions were mixed together and sonicated for 10 minutes. The solvothermal reaction was carried out at 50 °C for 3 days under a static condition. The precipitated product was collected by centrifugation at 5000 rpm, and washed with water, and subsequently washed with ethanol. The obtained yield is 12.4 g (fig. S4).

Synthesis of AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanoparticles ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{AlF}_5\text{N}_4\text{NiO}_3$)

Pyrazine ($\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}_2$, 1.80 g, 22.03 mmol) was dissolved in 9 ml of 2:1 (v/v) mixture ethanol- H_2O . Subsequently, nickel acetate tetrahydrate ($\text{Ni}(\text{OCOCH}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.20 g, 8.84 mmol) was added into the above solution and the solution was sonicated for 2 minutes. Separately, aluminum hydroxide ($\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$, 0.70 g, 8.97 mmol) was dissolved in 7 ml of 6:1 (v/v) mixture HF- H_2O . These two solutions were mixed together and sonicated for 5 minutes, a sky blue mixture was formed. The solvothermal reaction was carried

out at 80 °C for 6 hours under a static condition. The precipitated product was collected by centrifugation at 5000 rpm, and washed with total 300 ml of water, and subsequently washed with 60 ml of ethanol. Finally, nanosheets was dispersed in required amount of CHCl₃ solution.

AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanoparticles stock solution

To prevent agglomeration, nanoparticles was not dried before film casting and formation. Concentrations of nanoparticles in CHCl₃ solution was determined by drying 1 ml of aliquot to find the mass of nanoparticles, and resulting stock solutions were found to be 70 mg/ml.

Synthesis of FeFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets

Pyrazine (C₄H₄N₂, 1.80 g, 22.03 mmol) was dissolved in 9 ml of 2:1 (v/v) mixture ethanol-H₂O. Subsequently, nickel acetate tetrahydrate (Ni(OCOCH₃)₂·4H₂O, 2.20 g, 8.84 mmol) was added into the above solution and the solution was sonicated for 2 minutes. Separately, iron nitrate nonahydrate (Fe(NO₃)₂·9H₂O, 1.63 g, 4.03 mmol) was dissolved in 5 ml of 4:1 (v/v) mixture HF-H₂O. These two solutions were mixed together and sonicated for 3 minutes. The solvothermal reaction was carried out at 100 °C for 12 hours under a static condition. The precipitated product was collected by centrifugation at 5000 rpm, and washed with total 300 ml of water, and subsequently washed with 60 ml of ethanol (fig. S6).

Synthesis of Zn₂(Bim)₃ nanosheets and Zn-TCPP nanosheets

The above nanosheets were synthesized according to the reported procedures: Zn₂(Bim)₃ nanosheets (46), Zn-TCPP (47).

Synthesis of 6FDA-polyimide polymers

Polyimide polymers were synthesized *via* condensation of dianhydride monomers with a diamine (48,49). Typically, stoichiometric amounts of monomers and diamines were agitated and reacted in a 20 wt% 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP) solution under N₂ purge at low temperature (~ 5 °C) for 24 h to produce a high molecular weight polyamide acid (PAA) solution. Then chemical imidization was achieved in the presence of 3-methylpyridine and acetic anhydride at ambient temperature for 24 h under N₂ purge, and the resulting polyimide was precipitated and washed with methanol and dried at 210 °C under vacuum for 24 h. Monomers comprising (4,4' hexafluoroisopropylidene) diphthalic anhydride (6FDA) and 2,6-diaminotoluene (DAT) were used to synthesize 6FDA-DAT polymer. The molecular weight of the synthesized 6FDA-DAT was 164,000 g mol⁻¹ with a polydispersity index (PDI) of 1.92. Also, monomers comprising 6FDA, 2,4,6-trimethyl-1,3-phenylenediamine (DAM) and 2,6-diaminotoluene (DAT) were used to synthesize 6FDA-DAM-DAT with the DAM/DAT molar ratio of 1:1 according to reported procedure. The molecular weight of the synthesized 6FDA-DAM-DAT was 165,000 g mol⁻¹ with a polydispersity index (PDI) of 2.12. Prior use, 6FDA was purified once by vacuum sublimation, DAM and DAT were purified three times by vacuum sublimation. N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) was vacuum distilled immediately before use. Finally, all the polymer was precipitated into methanol, washed with methanol three times, and dried over several days under vacuum at 120 °C.

Membrane Fabrication

General: Membrane fabrication was performed in a glove bag filled with CHCl₃ or THF or DCM vapor in order to prevent a rapid solvent evaporation from the emerging membrane. Prior to gas adsorption and permeation measurements, membranes were thermally treated at 200 °C for 20 h under a dynamic vacuum to remove any residual solvent or water in polymers as well as within pores of MOF.

Pure polyimide membranes

Polyimides (6FDA-DAM, 6FDA-DAM-DAT or 6FDA-DAT) were dried in a vacuum oven at 150 °C overnight before being dissolved in CHCl₃. Pure polyimide (6FDA-DAM, 6FDA-DAM-DAT or 6FDA-DAT) membrane with desired thickness (typically 75 μm) was fabricated by dissolving 250 mg of dried polyimide in 3.5 mL of CHCl₃. The solution was mixed on a mechanical shaker overnight to dissolve the

polymer. The resulting casting solution was poured in a glass Petri dish on a leveled surface, which was placed in a glove bag pre-saturated with CHCl_3 vapour for at least 1 h. The film was left in the glove bag overnight to allow the CHCl_3 solvent to evaporate slowly.

[001]-oriented ((001)-AIFFFIVE/6FDA-polyimides) MMMOF membranes fabrications.

Uniformly 001-oriented AIFFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets mixed-matrix metal-organic framework (MMMOF) membranes were prepared by “slow evaporation-induced in plane alignment” of (001)-AIFFFIVE nanosheets in polymer matrix. MMMOF membranes with various nanosheets loading in a thickness range of 50-70 μm were fabricated by dissolving the appropriate amount of polyimides (6FDA-DAM, 6FDA-DAM-DAT or 6FDA-DAT) and (001)-AIFFFIVE nanosheets in CHCl_3 solvent.

Polymer solution preparation: A polymer solution was prepared by dissolving 150 mg of dried polyimides (6FDA-DAM, 6FDA-DAM-DAT or 6FDA-DAT) in 2 mL of CHCl_3 by shaking on a mechanical shaker for 3 h at room temperature.

MOF suspension preparation: A required amounts of aliquot from (001)-AIFFFIVE nanosheets stock solution (1.02 ml for 40 wt%, 1.50 ml for 50 wt% and 2.25 ml for 60 wt% MMMOF membranes) was added in a 25 ml glass vial and a required amount of CHCl_3 was added in order to maintain a total volume of 2.5 ml.

To this MOF suspension, 10% of the polymer solution was added and the suspension further stirred for 30 min (priming). After that, the remaining polymer solution was added to the MOF suspension and stirred for 150 minutes at 35 °C. The resulting casting solution was poured in a Teflon dish on a leveled surface, which was placed in a glove bag pre-saturated with CHCl_3 vapour for at least 1 h. The dish was left in the glove bag overnight at room temperature to allow the CHCl_3 solvent to evaporate slowly. The freestanding [001]-oriented MMMOF membrane was then dried in a vacuum oven at 200 °C for 20 h to remove any residual CHCl_3 .

Preparation of ultrathin (001)-AIFFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane on porous $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ support

Ultrathin (001)-AIFFFIVE(50)/6FDA-DAM-DAT MMMOF membrane was prepared on porous $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ support using the spin coating method. First, 1 wt% 6FDA-DAM-DAT was dissolved in CHCl_3 and the desired amounts of (001)-AIFFFIVE nanosheets (50 wt% relative to the total weight of the membrane) was added into the 6FDA-DAM-DAT solution. The mixed solution was stirred at 250 rpm for 150 minutes at 35 °C. Separately, a porous $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ disc was carefully polished using a SiC sandpaper (Presi, grit size P800) and washed with plenty of ethanol, and immersed in a CHCl_3 solution for 2 h to fill the pores of the support. Before spin-coating CHCl_3 droplet was wiped off. The nanosheets-polymer suspension was spin-coated onto $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ substrate at the speed of 1500 rpm for 30 sec. Immediately, the substrate was placed in CHCl_3 saturated glove bag and kept for 12 h at room temperature. Finally, ultrathin MMMOF membrane were dried at 200 °C under vacuum for 15 h.

Randomly arranged (001)-AIFFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT MMMOF membranes fabrications.

Randomly arranged (001)-AIFFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT MMMOF membrane was fabricated under the same conditions as for uniformly [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes but the glove bag was not saturated with CHCl_3 vapour so that the CHCl_3 solvent can evaporate first.

AIFFFIVE-1-Ni nanoparticles/6FDA-polyimides mixed-matrix membranes

Randomly arranged AIFFFIVE-1-Ni nanoparticles MMMs with various nanoparticles loading were fabricated under the same conditions as for uniformly [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes but using MOF nanoparticles suspension.

Nanosheets, nanoparticles and MMMOF membranes characterizations

Imaging of nanosheets, nanoparticles and MMMOF membranes:

The AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets or nanoparticles morphology and their orientation/alignment in MMMOF membranes were examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) FEI Nova Nano SEM450 and Magellan 400-FEG operating at an acceleration voltage of 3 kV and an emission current of 40 pA, and 1.5 kV and an emission current of 13 pA, respectively. SEM samples were prepared by dispersing the nanosheets or nanoparticles in ethanol and drop-casting onto an aluminium SEM pin stubs. In order to obtain cross-sectional SEM image, the MMMOF membrane was cryogenically fractured in liquid nitrogen to preserve their microstructures. To dissipate charge, the sample was sputter coated with ~3 nm of Iridium.

FIB-SEM analysis of [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes:

Focused ion beam scanning electron microscopy (FIB-SEM) experiments were performed in Helios G4 UX DualBeam (FEI) microscopes. Slices with a nominal thickness of 50 nm were milled away by the FIB, operating at 5 kV and 25 pA. Between 110 and 434 individual SEM micrographs of the consecutive cross-sections exposed on milling were recorded, at magnifications of 12,000-45,000, with a secondary electron detector operated at 1 kV. The stack of images was aligned to an external feature on the membrane surface using a cross-correlation algorithm, and a stretching operation in the y direction was performed to correct the foreshortening caused by the tilt angle between the specimen cross-section and the SEM detector.

Identification of MOF structure and nanosheets or nanoparticles orientation in MMMOF membranes:

The nanosheets structure and orientation was determined using X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. The XRD was collected on a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer (Cu K_{α} $\lambda=1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) in Bragg-Brentano θ - θ geometry with an operating power of 40 kV/40 mA and automatic divergence slit (irradiated length = 0.6 mm), and a flat plate sample holder. The data were collected at room temperature by the continuous-count method ($3^{\circ} \text{ min}^{-1}$) in the range $2\theta = 4-40^{\circ}$.

Quantifying of MOF nanosheets or nanoparticles loading in MMMOF membranes:

The loading of nanosheets or nanoparticles in mixed-matrix membrane was determined by a thermogravimetric analysis method using a TA Q-5000 analyzer. Typically ~10 mg of nanosheets or nanocrystals powder was first activated under flowing N_2 at 200 $^{\circ}C$ for 135 minutes to ensure activation, then heated to 800 $^{\circ}C$ at a heating rate of 10 $^{\circ}C \text{ min}^{-1}$ under flowing O_2 and temperature held at 800 $^{\circ}C$ for 2 h. The residual metal oxide mass was subsequently compared to the initial activated mass of the MOF. The same protocol was performed for nanosheets or nanoparticles containing mixed-matrix membranes. The percentage of mass remaining after 800 $^{\circ}C$ for 2 h under flowing O_2 is attributed to metal oxide, and from this mass the amount of activated nanosheets or nanoparticles present in the hybrid membranes was obtained. Typical TGA curves for determining the nanosheets or nanoparticles loading in the mixed-matrix membranes are shown in figs. S14.

Attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectra were recorded by a Thermo Scientific Nicolet 6700 spectrophotometer at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} with 64 scans in the spectral range $4000-600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and the corresponding IR spectra are shown in figs. S15.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

Tensile experiments were conducted using a Q800 DMA (TA Instruments) with a tensile clamp accessory in the controlled force mode. Films were first cut into strips that were 5.3 mm wide and approximately 25 mm long. Each strip was kept isothermal at 25 $^{\circ}C$ for 15 min, and the tensile force was ramped at 1 N/min until fracture. A minimum of three valid measurements were performed for each sample, which were characterized by a clean brittle fracture in the middle of the strip. The stress-strain curves shown in this work represent one of the measurements taken.

Rheological Characterization

The viscosities of the MOF-polymer suspension was determined using a Brookfield's CAP-2000+ Viscometer. The measurement was conducted at 35 °C, speed of rotation 400 RPM for 50 second using 38 μL MOF-polymer suspension.

Gas adsorption measurements

The gas adsorption measurements were performed using Micromeritics ASAP 2020 and Vstar vapor adsorption analyzer from Quantachrome instruments. Samples consisting of ~100 mg of nanosheets, nanoparticles, pure polymer membrane, or MMMOF membrane were loaded into a preweighed glass tube, and heated at 200 °C for 12 h under a dynamic vacuum. The mass of the activated sample was then used as the basis for the adsorption measurements. After an adsorption isotherm was measured, the sample was reactivated at 150 °C for 6 h before measuring a subsequent adsorption isotherm.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy

¹H NMR was run on a 400 MHz instrument using CDCl₃ as the solvent.

Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC)

The weight-averaged molecular weight, number-averaged molecular weight, and polydispersity index for the prepared polymer were estimated using an Agilent 1260 size exclusion chromatography (SEC) system calibrated relative to polystyrene and using tetrahydrofuran (THF) or chloroform (CHCl₃) as the solvent.

Gas permeation measurements

Pure gas permeation measurements:

Gas permeation properties of membrane was conducted using a permeation system that was constructed in-house (Fig. S46). The pure gas permeation properties were evaluated by a variable-pressure constant-volume methods at 35 °C and 2 atm for He, H₂, CO₂, O₂, N₂, CH₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆ and C₃H₈. Detailed description of the permeation cell set-up and testing procedure has been described elsewhere (50). The round membrane was mounted on the permeation cell and masked with adhesive aluminum tape and sealed by epoxy resins. On curing, a small area of membrane remained exposed, and the area of membrane accessible to gas transport was determined using a scanner. The membrane thickness was measured with a depth gauge. The permeation systems was evacuated at 35 °C for 12 h before performing any permeation test. The slope of downstream pressure vs. time (dp/dt) at the steady state condition was used for the calculation of gas permeability with accordance to the below equation:

$$P = \frac{Vl}{p_0ART} \frac{dp}{dt} \times 10^{10} \quad (1)$$

where P refers to the gas permeability of a membrane in barrer (1 barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm cm⁻² s⁻¹ cmHg⁻¹), V is the volume of downstream chamber (cm³), l is the membrane thickness (cm), p_0 is the upstream pressure (cmHg), A refers to the effective area of membrane (cm²), R is the gas constant (0.278 cm³ cmHg cm⁻³(STP) K⁻¹), T is the operating temperature (K).

The ideal selectivity of gas A to gas B, $\alpha_{A/B}$, was evaluated based on the equation as follows:

$$\alpha_{A/B} = \frac{P_A}{P_B} \quad (2)$$

where P_A and P_B denote the permeability of gases A and B, respectively.

Based on the solution-diffusion model, permeability is defined as a product of diffusivity (D) and solubility (S). Thus, ideal permeability selectivity (α_P) is the product of diffusivity selectivity (α_D) and solubility selectivity (α_S):

$$P = D \times S \quad (3)$$

$$\alpha_{A/B} = \alpha_P = \alpha_D \times \alpha_S = \frac{D_A}{D_B} \times \frac{S_A}{S_B} \quad (4)$$

where D_A and D_B are the diffusion coefficients for components A and B, respectively, with a unit of cm^2/s , whereas S_A and S_B are the solubility coefficients of components A and B, respectively, with a unit of $\text{cm}^3(\text{STP})/(\text{cm}^3 \text{cmHg})$.

The diffusivity coefficient D ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) was determined from the time lag method using the following equation:

$$D = \frac{l^2}{6\theta} \quad (5)$$

where l is the membrane thickness and θ is the time lag (s).

The solubility coefficient S ($\text{cm}^3 (\text{STP}) \text{cm}^{-3} \text{cmHg}^{-1}$), was obtained indirectly as the ratio of the permeability to the diffusion coefficient as following equation:

$$S = P/D \quad (6)$$

Maxwell Back-calculations.

We used the Maxwell model to predict the gas permeation properties of the mixed-matrix membrane and to back-calculate the permeability and selectivity of molecular sieve filler (fig.S47) (11). The model was originally developed by James C. Maxwell to predict the dielectric properties of the composite materials. The constructive equations governing electrical conduction and the flux through membranes are close analogs, permitting the applicability of Maxwell's equation to predict the gas transport properties in mixed matrix membranes. The Maxwell model is given by:

$$P_{\text{MMM}} = P_p \left[\frac{P_s + 2P_p - 2\phi_s(P_p - P_s)}{P_s + 2P_p + \phi_s(P_p - P_s)} \right] \quad (7)$$

where P_{MMM} is the permeability in the mixed matrix membrane; P_p is the permeability in the polymer matrix; P_s is the permeability in dispersed molecular sieve filler, and ϕ_s is the volume fraction of molecular sieve filler in the mixed matrix membrane. The major requirements for applying the Maxwell model are satisfied for our prediction. They are (i) the contact between two phases at the nanosheets-polymer interface are defect-free. (ii) The volume of the nanosheets is carefully calculated and the used value of a volume fraction of the nanosheet is less than 0.2 ($0 < \phi < 0.2$). (iii) The nanosheets are homogeneously distributed in a polymer matrix; (iv) The incorporation of nanosheets does not change the properties of the neighboring polymer phase.

Mixed gas permeation measurements:

A binary gas mixture (CO_2/CH_4 : 10/90; 20/80 and 50/50) and ternary gas mixture ($\text{H}_2\text{S}/\text{CO}_2/\text{CH}_4$: 1/9/90; 2/18/80 and 5/5/90) were used for mixed-gas permeation tests. The mixed-gas permeation measurement was performed using the modified single-gas permeation equipment integrated with micro-gas chromatography (Agilent 490 Micro-GC). Pure polymeric and MMMOF membranes were evaluated at a total mixed gas feed pressure of 2-35 bar at 25-100 °C. The stage cut (the flow rate ratio of permeate to feed) was maintained below 1% to avoid concentration polarization on the upstream side of the permeation cell and keep the driving force across the membrane constant throughout the course of the experiment. The gas mixture was allowed to permeate the membrane until a steady-state permeation rate was reached (>5 time lags). The permeate volume was then evacuated and allowed to accumulate under steady-state conditions. The permeate gas was then expanded into an evacuated volume and analyzed with a GC. The mixed gas permeability of component i was measured by following equation

$$P_i = 10^{10} \frac{y_i}{x_i p_0} \frac{V l}{ART} \frac{dp}{dt} \quad (8)$$

where y and x are the mole fractions in permeate and feed respectively, and the p_0 is the feed pressure of the component i .

The separation factor α was calculated as the ratio of the permeability of two components i and j .

$$\alpha_{i/j} = \frac{y_i/y_j}{x_i/x_j} \quad (9)$$

Supplementary Text

Atomic structure analysis of AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets

STEM analysis:

High-resolution spherical aberration-corrected (C_s -corrected) scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) was performed using a JEOL Grand ARM operated at 300 kV. The microscope is equipped with a cold field emission gun and a double corrector for the STEM and TEM modes assuring a point resolution in either case of 0.7 Å. Prior to AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets data acquisition, the nanosheets were dispersed by sonication for 10 minutes in absolute ethanol. Few drops of the suspension were placed onto a holey carbon copper microgrid.

STEM is the most appropriate technique for local atomic structure examination in porous materials. Nevertheless, MOFs are extremely electron beam sensitive to afford the attainment of high-resolution images. Thus, acquiring data is not straightforward and low dose techniques are imperative. Because of this major drawback, the number of frameworks analyzed using this technique is still relatively scarce. In the present work, we used the microscope in STEM mode, which focused the electron beam into a very fine spot (below 1 Å) and obtain enough structural information from the irradiated area, and then it is scanned over the area of interest, while the rest of the crystal remains ‘untouched’. This approach is very beneficial as it allows acquiring numerous images from a single MOF crystal. By controlling the e -beam dose, it allowed us to obtain very high-quality atomic resolution images of the extremely electron beam sensitive and ultra-microporous AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets. Furthermore, this technique permits the simultaneous acquisition of different signals, High Angle Annular Dark Field (HAADF), Annular Dark Field (ADF) together with Annular Bright Field (ABF) images. In the current study, both ADF and ABF detectors were simultaneously used, ADF is convenient for imaging the metal nodes, and ABF is useful for light materials imaging even under low-dose conditions. A more detailed analysis of ADF and ABF images is shown (fig. S7). Besides the opposite contrast between the two detectors, it is possible to appreciate in both cases a clear location of the metals that appear as bright or dark spots in the ADF and ABF images respectively. However, ABF provides a higher degree of information in terms of the lighter atoms.

Multi-slice STEM simulations:

To simulate the STEM-ADF data of the AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets along the [001] and [100] orientation we used the QSTEM program (51). The crystal supercell dimensions used were $48.28 \times 103.22 \times 23.8$ Å³, where 20 Å was used as ideal thickness because of the good match between the experimental and simulated data and because of the information that was obtained from the SEM observations. The parameters used were: $C_s = 0$ mm, $U_{acc} = 300$ kV, an inner collection angle of 20 mrad and half-convergence angle of 15 mrad.

Computational Methods

AIFVIVE-1-Ni microscopic surface model

The crystal structure of AIFVIVE-1-Ni was taken from our previous experimental work (25). This structure was first geometry optimized at the Density Functional Theory (DFT) level with both the positions of the atoms of the framework and the cell parameters fully relaxed. These calculations were performed

using the Vienna *ab initio* Simulation Package (VASP, version 5.4.4) (52) with a plane wave energy cutoff of 650 eV and convergence criteria of 10^{-5} eV and 10^{-2} eV/Å respectively for the energy and sum of the atomic forces. The $2s^22p^2$, $1s^1$, $3d^84s^2$, $3s^23p^1$, $2s^22p^5$, and $2s^22p^3$ atomic orbitals were treated as valence states for C, H, Ni, Al, F, and N, respectively. The electronic exchange-correlation interaction was treated using the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) functional within the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) (53,54). The first Brillouin zone was set with a $3\times3\times2$ Monkhorst–Pack special k -point mesh. The van der Waals correction DFT-D3 method was used to accurately account for long-range dispersion interactions (55). In order to better describe the d states of Ni in the AIFIVE-1-Ni model, an Hubbard U correction of 6.4 eV was applied consistent with previous works reported on Ni-containing systems (56,25). The resulting DFT-optimized cell parameters are in excellent agreement with the corresponding experimental data as reported in table S17.

This DFT optimized structure model was further employed to construct an atomistic AIFIVE-1-Ni surface model. In accordance to the experimental STEM images (Fig. 2A), the plane (001) was chosen to orient the cleavage of the surface. The resulting surface slab model slab has a z -length of approximately 42.65 Å (fig. S28) to avoid the surface to interact with itself due to periodic boundary conditions and its dimension along the x and y directions is 9.79 Å. The resulting model has a zero dipole in the direction perpendicular to the surface slab (57). This surface model was then geometry-optimized using the same level of theory and parameters as for the optimization of the bulk model.

Partial atomic charges were calculated for this surface model using the density derived electrostatic and chemical (DDEC) method (58) as implemented in the VASP package.

A final surface slab model was then constructed to be further used in the force field simulations by duplicating 5 times the surface model in the x and y directions giving final x and y lengths of 48.93 Å (fig. S28). In these calculations, this surface slab model was treated as a fully flexible framework with intramolecular potential parameters taken from the Universal Force Field (UFF) (59) while 12-6 Lennard-Jones (LJ) van der Waals and coulombic contributions were considered to model the intermolecular interactions. The 12-6 LJ parameters were taken from the generic forcefields DREIDING (60) and UFF (59) for the atoms of the organic and inorganic nodes respectively. Fig. S28 provides an illustration of the atom types present in the AIFIVE-1-Ni (001) surface model and table S18 lists their respective charges and van der Waals parameters.

This flexible force field implemented for the description of AIFIVE-1-Ni (001) surface model was validated by using Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations in the NPT ensemble using the Berendsen thermostat and barostat with a relaxation time of 0.1 ps and 0.5 ps respectively. The resulting force field relaxed cell parameters and geometric features are in good agreement with those obtained for the DFT-optimized crystal structures (table S19).

6FDA-DAM microscopic model

The 6FDA-DAM polymer model was taken from our previous work (61). It was constructed starting with a united-atom monomer illustrated in fig. S28C and applying a controlled polymerization procedure that involves several MD cycles performed with the LAMMPS package (62) followed by the corresponding linking of the monomeric units, as implemented in the *polymatic* code (63). A detailed workflow of the computational approach can be found in our previous works (63). The terminations of the resulting polymer were achieved as follows: on one end, the replacement of a nitrogen atom (N17 in fig. S28C) by an oxygen atom and, on the other end, the addition of $-\text{NH}_2$ group to a carbon atom (C30 in fig. S28C). This polymer model was treated as fully flexible in our calculations: bonded interactions were modeled using the analytical expression and parameters described by the generic forcefield GAFF while the non-bonded

interactions were treated by a 12-6 LJ potential contribution and a coulombic term, with parameters taken from our previous work (61) and reminded in table S20.

AIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM microscopic composite model

The construction of the (001)-AIIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM composite model was obtained using the computational strategy we previously developed and validated on a series of MOF/Polymer systems (64). First, the atomic coordinates of the 6FDA-DAM polymer model were unwrapped in the z-direction and the simulation box was adjusted according to the lattice parameters of the (001)-AIIFFIVE-1-Ni structure model leading to a system with the following dimension $48.93 \text{ \AA} \times 48.93 \text{ \AA} \times 170.00 \text{ \AA}$, including the presence of the vacuum in the z direction. Then, the 6FDA-DAM model was brought into contact with the AIIFFIVE-1-Ni slab model, and submitted to a 21-steps MD simulation routine integrating NVT and NPT cycles with T and P kept constant by using the Berendsen thermostat and barostat with respective relaxation times of 0.1 ps and 0.5 ps in a modified version of the DL_POLY Classic code (65). This procedure allowed the equilibration of the polymer, leading to a well-packed (001)-AIIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM MMMOF membrane. The interactions between the MOF surface and the polymer were treated by a sum of 12-6 LJ van der Waals and coulombic terms, the cross 12-6 LJ parameters were obtained using the Lorentz Berthelot mixing rules. The two components of the composite were treated as fully flexible with the force field parameters detailed above. The van der Waals interactions were handled with a 12 \AA cutoff while the electrostatic interactions were calculated using the Ewald summation method (66) with a tolerance of 10^{-6} . NVT (T = 300 K) MD calculations were performed during a total simulation time of 10 nanoseconds (ns) with a time step of 1 femtosecond (fs). 10 independent (001)-AIIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM composites were built in order to improve the statistics by circumventing the fact that several configurations may be trapped in local minima. The interface formed between the two components of the composite was further characterized by calculating the distribution of the minimum MOF/polymer site-to-site distances at the interface (fig. S27, C and F, and fig. S29).

Prediction of the adsorption/separation properties of the AIIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM composite

Single-component (CO_2 , CH_4) and equimolar binary mixture adsorption isotherms were calculated for the AIIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM composite by grand canonical Monte Carlo (GCMC) simulations at 298 K. These calculations were carried out using a simulation box including the (001)-AIIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM model described above. Gas/composite interactions were described by a sum of coulombic and 12-6 LJ contributions. The former ones were obtained implementing the Ewald summation (66) with a 10^{-6} precision while the latter one was calculated considering a 12 \AA cutoff radius. For each state point of these simulations, 1×10^5 Monte Carlo cycles following 5×10^3 equilibration cycles (number of steps = number of cycles \times number of molecules) were used as implemented in the RASPA software (67). The composite was described using the force field parameters detailed above. CO_2 was described by the EPM2 model (68) corresponding to 3 atom-centered charged LJ sites while CH_4 was modeled by a single uncharged LJ site, as described by the united-atom TraPPE model (69). LJ crossed parameters were calculated using the Lorentz-Berthelot mixing rules. The adsorption enthalpies of each component were evaluated using the revised Widom's test particle insertion method (70). Preferential interactions/locations of the guest species were evaluated through a careful inspection of the representative snapshots and the calculations of several radial distribution functions (RDFs) between guests and composite averaged over all the GCMC configurations.

Figs. S1 to S47

Fig. S1.

Effects of pillar ratio on the morphology of AlFFIVE-1-Ni. (A to D) SEM images of AlFFIVE-1-Ni bulk crystals obtained using a synthetic gel with the pillar $[\text{AlF}_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2-}$ ratio of (A) 1, (B) 0.71, (C) 0.46, and (D) 0.32 with respect to Ni(II) in the gel. The solvothermal reaction performed at 100 °C for 3h.

Fig. S2.

Effect of reaction temperature and time on the morphology of AlFFIVE-1-Ni. (A to E) SEM images of AlFFIVE-1-Ni obtained from solvothermal reaction carried out at 100 °C for (A) 3h, and (B) 3 days. At 50 °C for (C) 3h, (D) 3 days without Ethanol, (E) 3 days with Ethanol.

Fig. S3.

Effect of amount of ethanol on the morphology of AlFFIVE-1-Ni. (A to E) SEM images of AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets obtained from solvothermal reaction using various ethanol/water mixture solution, the reactions were performed (A to D) at 50 °C for 3 days, and (E) 100 °C for 12 h.

Fig. S4.

Scale-up synthesis of AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets. (A and B) photographs of AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets crystallite synthesized in 12.4 g scale. (C) SEM image, (D) PXRD patterns, and (E) CO₂ adsorption isotherms at 298 K.

Fig. S5.

CO₂ adsorption isotherms on as-synthesized nanosheets, nanoparticles and bulk crystals of AlFFIVE-1-Ni measured at 308 K.

Fig. S6.

(A to C) SEM images of FeFFIVE-1-Ni (KAUST-9) crystals. (A) as-synthesized bulk FeFFIVE-1-Ni crystals and (B and C) FeFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets morphology under different magnifications.

Fig. S7.

C_s-corrected STEM analyses of AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets. (A to F) C_s-corrected STEM-ADF and ABF micrographs of a nanosheets along the [001] orientation. (B) The Electron Diffraction (ED) pattern of nanosheets corroborating the excellent crystallinity as well as [001] crystal orientation. (C) ADF image and (D) ABF image along [001] orientation. Symmetry averaged *p4mm* (E) ADF image and (F) ABF image.

Fig. S8.

(A) Low resolution ADF image of AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheet. (B) High-resolution ABF image along the [001] orientation, the corresponding ED pattern (inset) indexed assuming $I4/mcm$ symmetry. (C) Symmetry averaged atomic-resolution ABF image, the strong dark spots corresponds to the $-F-Ni-F-Al-F-$ inorganic columns. The elongated faint signal between $-F-Ni-F-Al-F-$ inorganic columns is attributed to the pyrazine, for clarity, the crystal structure is superimposed.

Fig. S9.

(**A**) Low-resolution ADF image showing AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets along a different orientation. (**B**) Low- and (**C**) High-resolution ABF image along $[100]$ orientation. (**D**) Wiener filtered image along $[100]$ orientation that allows the clear visualization of Ni(II)-pyrazine-Ni(II) 2D square grids (black layers) separated each other by 7.2 \AA , for clarity, the crystal structure is superimposed. Color code: Ni(II) orange, Al(III) purple, C gray, F green, N blue.

Fig. S10.

Effects of solvents as a dispersion medium for membrane preparation on the performance of CO₂/CH₄ separation. (A) 6FDA-DAM (PI) and (001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM (MMM) membranes; (B) 6FDA-DAM-DAT (PI) and (001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT(MMM) membranes. Pure CO₂ permeation at 1 bar and pure CH₄ permeation at 4 bar, at 35 °C. 1 Barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm/cm² s cmHg. Tetrahydrofuran (THF), dichloromethane (DCM), Chloroform (CHCl₃).

Fig. S11.

Representative structures of polyimide polymers employed for membrane preparation in this study.
6FDA-DAM [6FDA: 4,4'-(hexafluoroisopropylidene) diphthalic anhydride; DAM: 2,4,6 trimethyl-1,3-diaminobenzene].
6FDA-DAM-DAT(1:1) [6FDA: 4,4'-(hexafluoroisopropylidene) diphthalic anhydride; DAM: 2,4,6 trimethyl-1,3-diaminobenzene; DAT: 2,6-diaminotoluene].
6FDA-DAT [6FDA: 4,4'-(hexafluoroisopropylidene) diphthalic anhydride; DAT: 2,6-diaminotoluene].

Fig. S12.

(A and B) Cross-sectional SEM images of pure 6FDA-DAM membrane. (C and D) Cross-sectional SEM images of uniformly in plane aligned (001)-AlFFIVE/6FDA-DAM MMM under different magnification with (001)-AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets loading of 58.9 wt%.

Fig. S13.

FIB-SEM analyses of [001]-oriented ((001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM) MMMOF membrane. (A) Top view SEM image of the trench carved with a FIB on the surface of (001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM membrane. The white line frame indicates a central region within the imaged cross-section that was selected for further analysis. (B and C) Representative SEM images of cross-sections of the membrane containing (001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets embedded in 6FDA-DAM polyimide under different magnification. A uniform in-plane alignment of (001)-AIFVIVE nanosheets appear as bright motifs on the dark grey polymer matrix (B and C).

Fig. S14.

TGA curves of AIFFIVE-1-Ni powder, AIFFIVE-1-Ni/polymer MMMs with different MOF loadings and pure polymer membrane. **(A)** nanoparticle/6FDA-DAM MMMs, **(B)** (001)-AIFFIVE/6FDA-DAM MMMOF membranes, **(C)** (001)-AIFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT(1:1) MMMOF membranes, and **(D)** (001)-AIFFIVE/6FDA-DAT MMMOF membranes. Samples were first heated at 200 °C under N₂ for 2 h to remove any residual solvent or moisture. Afterwards, the temperature was increased to 800 °C with a constant heating rate of 10 °C /min under O₂ to decompose 6FDA-DAM, and MOFs to corresponding metal oxidize.

Fig. S15.

ATR-FTIR spectra of AIFVIVE-1-Ni powder, AIFVIVE-1-Ni/polymer MMMs with different MOF loadings and pure polymer membrane. (A) nanoparticle/6FDA-DAM MMMs, (B) (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM MMMOF membranes, (C) (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT(1:1) MMMOF membranes, and (D) (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAT MMMOF membranes.

Fig. S16.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of AIFVIVE-1-Ni powder, AIFVIVE-1-Ni/polymer MMMs with different MOF loadings and pure polymer membrane. **(A)** nanoparticle/6FDA-DAM MMMs, **(B)** (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM MMMOF membranes, **(C)** (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT(1:1) MMMOF membranes, and **(D)** (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAT MMMOF membranes.

Fig. S17.

(A and B) Cross-sectional SEM images of uniformly in plane aligned (001)-AlFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT MMMOF membrane under different magnification with (001)-AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets loading of 59.6 wt%.

Fig. S18.

FIB-SEM analysis of [001]-oriented ((001)-AlFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT) MMMOF membrane. (A) Top view SEM image of the trench carved with a FIB on the surface of (001)-AlFFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane. The white line frame indicates a central region within the imaged cross-section that was selected for further analysis. (B and C) Representative SEM images of cross-sections of the membrane containing (001)-AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets embedded in 6FDA-DAM-DAT polyimide under different magnification. (B and C) A uniform in-plane alignment of (001)-AlFFIVE nanosheets appear as bright motifs on the dark grey polymer matrix.

Fig. S19.

FIB-SEM analysis of (001)-AlFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane with 59.6 wt% nanosheets loading. (A) Cross-section SEM image. (B and C) FIB-SEM images of the cross-section of the membrane from the (B) top side and (C) bottom side. (B and C) A homogeneous in-plane alignment of (001)-AlFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets appears as bright motifs on the dark grey polymer matrix.

Fig. S20.

(A and B) Cross-sectional SEM images of uniformly in plane aligned (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAT MMMOF membrane under different magnification with (001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets loading of 60.3 wt%.

Fig. S21.

(A and B) Cross-sectional SEM images of nanoparticles/6FDA-DAM MMMs under different magnification with AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanoparticles loading of 37.1 wt%.

Fig. S22.

Stress–strain curves of 6FDA-DAM, nanoparticles/6FDA-DAM, and nanosheets/6FDA-DAM membranes at different MOF loadings.

Fig. S23.

(A and C) A comparison of mixed-gas CO₂ permeability and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity of (001)-AIFFIVE nanosheets(*ns*)/polymer and AIFFIVE nanoparticles(*np*)/polymer membranes based on by volume (%) and (B and D) by weight (%). Permeation conditions: CO₂/CH₄:50/50, at 2 bar, 35 °C.

Fig. S24.

(A and B) Cross-sectional SEM images of randomly aligned (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane under different magnification with (001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets loading of 48.9 wt%. (C) A comparison of CO₂ permeability and CO₂/CH₄ selectivity of randomly aligned and in-plane aligned (001)-AIFVIVE nanosheets MMMOF membranes. Permeation conditions: CO₂ feed pressure 1 bar and CH₄ feed pressure at 4 bar, at 35 °C.

Fig. S25.

(A) A comparison of CO_2/CH_4 separation of MMMs comprises of MOF nanosheets with different pore size and shape, functionality, and host-guest interactions. 12.1 wt% $\text{Zn}_2(\text{bim})_4$, 13.5 wt% Zn-TCPP, 11.3 and 58.9 wt% (001)-AIFVIVE nanosheets in 6FDA-DAM polymer. Permeation conditions: CO_2/CH_4 :50/50, at 2 bar, 35 °C. (B) CO_2 adsorption isotherms of $\text{Zn}_2(\text{bim})_4$, Zn-TCPP, and (001)-AIFVIVE nanosheets obtained at 35 °C.

Fig. S26.

CO₂ and CH₄ adsorption isotherms of (A) (001)-AIFVIVE nanosheets, (001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM membrane and pure 6FDA-DAM membrane. (B) (001)-AIFVIVE nanosheets, (001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane and pure 6FDA-DAM-DAT (1:1) membrane. (C) (001)-AIFVIVE nanosheets, (001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT membrane and pure 6FDA-DAT membrane. Isotherms measured at 35 °C. The star indicates the theoretical CO₂ uptake of MMMOF membranes.

Fig. S27.

Molecular modelling of (001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni/polymer MMMs. (A to F) Side views of the MOF/polymer interface model and associated pore distribution alongside the distribution of the MOF/polymer minimum separating distances: (A to C) 42 wt% (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM loaded composite model with and (D to F) 59 wt% (001)-AIFVIVE nanosheets loaded. F, N, O, C, Ni, Al and H atoms are respectively shown in green, blue, red, gray, orange, purple and white. C atoms of the polymer are shown in cyan for clarity. Green dots and red dots in fig. B and E denote to regions containing smaller and larger porosity respectively.

Fig. S28.

(A) Illustration of the AIFFIVE-1-Ni (001) surface model viewed along indicated directions. (B) Atom types associated with the AIFFIVE-1-Ni (001) surface model. Only a single end of the surface slab structure is shown in this scheme for clarity. F, N, C, Ni, Al and H are respectively shown in green, blue, gray, orange, purple and white. (C) Optimized 6FDA-DAM monomer structure, with head and tail atoms represented by atoms 17 and 30. N, C, O and H are respectively shown in blue, gray, red and white. (D) Atomic density profile of 6FDA-DAM (black) and AIFFIVE-1-Ni (red) in the AIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM composite plotted along the direction perpendicular to the surface slab (z).

Fig. S29.

(A) Lateral view (xz plane) of a representative interface of a AlFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM composite model displaying its adsorption surface (in blue) and showing the average 3.5 Å center-to-center MOF-polymer distance obtained from fig. S27. (B) Top view (xy plane) of such interface cut at a 3.5 Å height from the MOF surface highlighting the interconnected interfacial porosities.

Fig. S30.

(A and B) Representative snapshots obtained from single adsorption GCMC calculations at 298 K and 1 bar showing the main adsorption sites and interactions of CO₂ (red spheres) and CH₄ (blue spheres) in the AIFVIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM composite. (C) Radial distribution functions (RDFs) respectively displaying the interactions of CO₂ and CH₄ with the H atoms of the pyrazine of the MOF (black lines), with the O atoms of the carbonyl functions of the polymer (red lines) and with the CH₃ groups of the polymer (blue lines) obtained from single-component GCMC calculations for the composite at 1 bar and 298 K.

Fig. S31.

(A and B) Representative GCMC simulated snapshot for the adsorption of (A) CO₂ (red spheres) and (B) CH₄ (cyan spheres) in AIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM membrane at 298 K and 1 bar. (C) GCMC simulated binary mixture (solid symbols) and single component (empty symbols) adsorption isotherms at 298 K for AIFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-DAM composite.

Fig. S32.

Single gas permeability as a function of the kinetic diameters of various gases in **(A)** (001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM and pure 6FDA-DAM, **(B)** (001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT and pure 6FDA-DAM-DAT, **(C)** (001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT and pure 6FDA-DAT. Permeation measured at 2 bar and 35 °C.

Fig. S33.

(A and B) Single and mixed gas permeation under different feed CO₂ concentration (10-50%). Variation of CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability as a function of CO₂ concentration for (001)-AIFFIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM and 6FDA-DAM membranes, **(A)** single- and **(B)** mixed-gas. A comparison of single- and mixed-gas CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability at indicated CO₂/CH₄ composition for **(C)** 6FDA-DAM, and **(D)** (001)-AIFFIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM membranes. Permeation condition: CO₂/CH₄: 50/50 at 2 bar; 20/80 at 5 bar; 10/90 at 10 bar, at 35 °C.

Note for fig. S33 to S35:

Variation of single- and mixed-gas CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability were evaluated under similar CO₂ and CH₄ partial pressure. Therefore, we measured single gas permeation at CO₂ (1 bar)/CH₄ (9 bar), CO₂ (1 bar)/CH₄ (4 bar), CO₂ (1 bar)/CH₄ (1 bar), and mixed gas permeation under CO₂/CH₄: 10/90 at 10 bar, 20/80 at 5 bar, and 50/50 at 2 bar, respectively.

Fig. S34.

(A and B) Single and mixed gas permeation under different feed CO_2 concentration (10-50%). Variation of CO_2/CH_4 selectivity and CO_2 permeability as a function of CO_2 concentration for (001)-AIFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT and 6FDA-DAM-DAT membranes, **(A)** single- and **(B)** mixed-gas. A comparison of single- and mixed-gas CO_2/CH_4 selectivity and CO_2 permeability at indicated CO_2/CH_4 composition for **(C)** 6FDA-DAM-DAT, and **(D)** (001)-AIFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT membranes. Permeation condition: CO_2/CH_4 : 50/50 at 2 bar; 20/80 at 5 bar; 10/90 at 10 bar, at 35 °C.

Fig. S35.

(A and B) Single and mixed gas permeation under different feed CO_2 concentration (10-50%). Variation of CO_2/CH_4 selectivity and CO_2 permeability as a function of CO_2 concentration for (001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT and 6FDA-DAT membranes, **(A)** single- and **(B)** mixed-gas. A comparison of single- and mixed-gas CO_2/CH_4 selectivity and CO_2 permeability at indicated CO_2/CH_4 composition for **(C)** 6FDA-DAT, and **(D)** (001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT membranes. Permeation condition: CO_2/CH_4 : 50/50 at 2 bar; 20/80 at 5 bar; 10/90 at 10 bar, at 35 °C.

Fig. S36.

(A and B) Variable temperature (20-100 °C) CO₂/CH₄ separation under single gas (SG) and mixed gas (MG). Variation of CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability as a function of temperature for (001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM and 6FDA-DAM membranes, **(A)** single- and **(B)** mixed-gas. A comparison of single- and mixed-gas CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability at different temperatures for **(C)** 6FDA-DAM, and **(D)** (001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM membranes.

Fig. S37.

(A and B) Variable temperature (20-100 °C) CO₂/CH₄ separation under single gas (SG) and mixed gas (MG). Variation of CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability as a function of temperature for (001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT and 6FDA-DAM-DAT membranes, **(A)** single- and **(B)** mixed-gas. A comparison of single- and mixed-gas CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability at different temperatures for **(C)** 6FDA-DAM-DAT, and **(D)** (001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT membranes.

Fig. S38.

(A and B) Variable temperature (20-100 °C) CO₂/CH₄ separation under single gas (SG) and mixed gas (MG). Variation of CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability as a function of temperature for (001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT and 6FDA-DAT membranes, **(A)** single- and **(B)** mixed-gas. A comparison of single- and mixed-gas CO₂/CH₄ selectivity and CO₂ permeability at different temperatures for **(C)** 6FDA-DAT, and **(D)** (001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT membranes.

Fig. S39.

(A to C) Solubility, diffusivity, sorption and diffusion selectivity. Solubility and diffusivity of **(A)** CO₂ and **(B)** CH₄, and **(C)** CO₂/CH₄ sorption selectivity and diffusion selectivity in (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT and pure 6FDA-DAM-DAT membranes obtained temperature between 20 and 100 °C, feed pressure CO₂ at 1 bar and CH₄ at 4 bar. **(D)** Variable temperature CO₂ adsorption isotherms on (001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets.

Fig. S40.

(A) Plot of CO₂/CH₄ selectivity versus CO₂ permeability providing a recent literature review of MOFs-nanosheets/polymer-based MMMs. filled symbols: MMMs, empty symbols: pure polymers. (B) Comparison with the performance of our newly designed [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes.

Fig. S41.

A comparison of CO₂/CH₄ separation performances of 421 nm ultrathin (001)-AIFVIVE(55)/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane on porous α -Al₂O₃ support and 61 μ m thick free standing (001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT. Permeation conditions: CO₂ feed pressure 1 bar and CH₄ feed pressure 4 bar, at 35 °C.

Fig. S42.

(A and B) Membrane stability under different H₂S concentration, (A) H₂S/CO₂/CH₄: 1/9/90; (B) H₂S/CO₂/CH₄: 5/5/90. Robust H₂S/CO₂/CH₄ separation properties of (001)-AIFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane for at least 30 days. Feed pressure at 10 bar and 35 °C.

Fig. S43.

(A and B) High-pressure H₂S/CO₂/CH₄ permeation study. Permeability and selectivity of (A) (001)-AIFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM and (B) (001)-AIFIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM membranes for the separation of H₂S/CO₂/CH₄: 1/9/90 gas mixture under feed pressure varied from 5 to 35 bar, at 35 °C.

Fig. S44.

A comparison of high-pressure $H_2S/CO_2/CH_4$ permeation study. Permeability and selectivity of (001)-AIFFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT and pure 6FDA-DAM-DAT membranes for the separation of $H_2S/CO_2/CH_4$:1/9/90 gas mixture under feed pressure varied from 5 to 35 bar, at 35 °C.

Fig. S45.

Permeation properties of (001)-AIFVIVE(59.2)/6FDA-DAM-DAT MMMOF membranes for other gas pairs and comparison with 2008 Robeson upper-bounds (3): **(A)** H_2/N_2 , **(B)** H_2/CH_4 , **(C)** H_2/C_3H_6 and **(D)** H_2/C_3H_8 . Permeation conditions: pure gas feed pressure 2 bar, 35 °C. See table S4 for details information.

Fig. S46.
Constant-volume dense film permeation system for pure and mixed gases.

Fig. S47.
Theoretically predicting permeation properties of mixed-matrix membranes based on the measured performance of pure 6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane and (001)-AIFFIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT mixed-matrix membranes (Exp.: measured pure-gas permeability and selectivity; Pred.: Maxwell-predicted pure-gas permeability and selectivity).

Table S1 to S20

Table. S1. Effects of solvents on membrane fabrication for the permeation properties of the pure polymer and (001)-AIFVIVE MMMs.

Membranes	CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)			CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity		
	THF	DCM	CHCl ₃	THF	DCM	CHCl ₃
6FDA-DAM	903.4	874.3	881.9	19.3	19.8	20.3
(001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM	1325.6	1416.3	1295.7	26.4	24.2	32.8
6FDA-DAM-DAT	309.6	281.8	289.7	33.7	36.2	35.1
(001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	611.3	683.2	588.6	64.5	60.2	81.6

Pure CO₂ permeation at 1 bar and pure CH₄ permeation at 4 bar, permeation measured at 35 °C. 1 barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm/cm² s cmHg. Tetrahydrofuran (THF), dichloromethane (DCM), Chloroform (CHCl₃).

Table. S2. Physical properties of solvents.

Solvents	RP	Density (g/ml)	BP (°C)
THF	0.207	0.886	66.0
DCM	0.309	1.326	39.8
CHCl ₃	0.259	1.498	61.2

Table. S3. Mechanical properties of MOFs containing MMMs at 298 K.

Membranes	MOF loading (wt%)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Breaking elongation (%)	Ref.
AIFVIVE- <i>np</i> /6FDA-DAM	26.3	1.30	3.59	<i>This work</i>
	37.1	1.87	1.58	
	34.6	1.36	8.01	
(001)-AIFVIVE- <i>ns</i> /6FDA-DAM	46.9	1.79	5.84	
	58.9	3.35	1.64	
UiO-66-CN/PIM-1	20	1.26	4.30	71
UiO-66-CN/sPIM-1	20	1.30	3.45	
NbOFFIVE-1-Ni/6FDA-Durene	33	1.55	2.35	72
Zn(pyrz) ₂ (SiF ₆)/6FDA-TMPDA	20	1.15	na	73
UiO-66-NH ₂ /ODPA-DAM	27	na	2.05	74
UiO-66-NH ₂ @PI/ODPA-DAM	27	na	2.85	
MIL-101/SPEEK	40	1.42	na	75
ZIF-7/PI	50	0.50	4.5	76

np : nanoparticles, *ns* : nanosheets; na : not available.

Table. S4. Single gas permeation properties of [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes, and pure polymeric membranes using 9 different gas molecules.

Membranes	Permeability (barrer)								
	He	H ₂	CO ₂	O ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₆	C ₃ H ₆	C ₃ H ₈
6FDA-DAM	804.2	1016.5	841.4	163.0	48.2	43.9	29.1	32.2	3.0
(001)-AIFFFIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM	1416.0	1925.6	1243.5	319.2	68.1	42.4	27.1	25.1	2.7
6FDA-DAM-DAT	270.1	341.6	277.9	57.6	13.3	8.9	3.9	5.7	0.4
(001)-AIFFFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	675.9	908.6	524.3	120.6	24.5	7.6	2.3	2.9	0.3
6FDA-DAT	105.3	118.3	63.4	14.0	2.7	1.5	0.5	0.6	0.2
(001)-AIFFFIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT	198.5	259.5	132.5	26.1	4.8	1.2	0.3	0.3	0.1
Membranes	Selectivity								
	He/H ₂	H ₂ /CO ₂	O ₂ /N ₂	H ₂ /N ₂	N ₂ /CH ₄	CO ₂ /N ₂	CO ₂ /CH ₄	H ₂ /CH ₄	H ₂ /C ₃ H ₈
6FDA-DAM	0.8	1.2	3.4	21.1	1.1	17.5	19.6	23.2	344.6
(001)-AIFFFIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM	0.7	1.5	4.7	28.3	1.6	18.3	29.3	45.4	713.2
6FDA-DAM-DAT	0.8	1.2	4.3	25.7	1.5	20.9	31.2	38.3	776.4
(001)-AIFFFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	0.7	1.7	4.9	37.0	3.2	21.4	69.3	120.2	3494.7
6FDA-DAT	0.9	1.9	5.2	43.7	1.9	23.4	43.7	81.6	788.7
(001)-AIFFFIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT	0.8	2.0	5.4	54.1	3.9	27.6	106.9	209.3	2595.0

Gas permeation at 2 atm at 35 °C. 1 barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm/cm² s cmHg; 1 atm = 101 kPa.

Table. S5. Single gas CO₂/CH₄ separation performances of [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes at different nanosheets loading.

Membranes	Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity	Enhancement (%)	
	CO ₂	CH ₄		<i>P</i>	<i>S</i>
6FDA-DAM	881.9	43.4	20.3	0.0	0.0
(001)-AIFFFIVE(34.6)/6FDA-DAM	1021.5	40.7	25.1	15.8	23.5
(001)-AIFFFIVE(46.9)/6FDA-DAM	1186.3	40.3	29.4	34.5	44.9
(001)-AIFFFIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM	1295.7	39.5	32.8	46.9	61.4
6FDA-DAM-DAT	289.7	8.3	35.1	0.0	0.0
(001)-AIFFFIVE(34.1)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	403.7	7.5	53.9	39.4	53.5
(001)-AIFFFIVE(46.4)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	480.9	7.2	66.4	66.0	89.2
(001)-AIFFFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	588.6	7.2	81.6	103.2	132.5
6FDA-DAT	67.9	1.3	52.2	0.0	0.0
(001)-AIFFFIVE(32.8)/6FDA-DAT	96.6	1.2	80.5	42.3	54.1
(001)-AIFFFIVE(48.5)/6FDA-DAT	119.2	1.2	99.1	75.6	89.7
(001)-AIFFFIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT	148.3	1.2	122.1	118.4	133.8

Pure CO₂ permeation at 1 atm and pure CH₄ permeation at 4 atm, permeation measured at 35 °C. 1 barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm/cm² s cmHg.

Table. S6. Single and mixed gas permeation under different feed CO₂ concentration on 6FDA-DAM and (001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM membrane.

Single gas						Mixed gas					
Feed pressure (psi)		CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity		Feed CO ₂ :CH ₄ ratio	Feed Pressure (psi)	CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity	
CO ₂	CH ₄	PI	MMM	PI	MMM			PI	MMM	PI	MMM
15	15			19.5	29.3	50:50	30	873.4	1287.4	20.9	39.6
15	60	881.9	1295.7	20.3	32.8	20:80	75	804.6	1198.8	21.1	40.4
15	130			21.8	33.5	10:90	150	730.2	1095.4	20.6	41.2

Permeation measured at 35 °C. 1 Barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm/cm² s cmHg.

Table. S7. Single and mixed gas permeation under different feed CO₂ concentration on 6FDA-DAM-DAT and (001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane.

Single gas						Mixed gas					
Feed pressure (psi)		CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity		Feed CO ₂ :CH ₄ ratio	Feed Pressure (psi)	CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity	
CO ₂	CH ₄	PI	MMM	PI	MMM			PI	MMM	PI	MMM
15	15			33.0	74.7	50:50	30	280.5	578.0	35.9	78.3
15	60	289.7	588.6	35.1	81.6	20:80	75	241.6	505.8	35.4	82.7
15	130			36.7	87.9	10:90	150	204.7	435.9	34.8	84.7

Permeation measured at 35 °C. 1 barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm/cm² s cmHg.

Table. S8. Single and mixed gas permeation under different feed composition on 6FDA-DAT and (001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT membrane.

Single gas						Mixed gas					
Feed pressure (psi)		CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity		Feed CO ₂ :CH ₄ ratio	Feed Pressure (psi)	CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity	
CO ₂	CH ₄	PI	MMM	PI	MMM			PI	MMM	PI	MMM
15	15			46.1	107.7	50:50	30	66.4	146.5	53.3	119.7
15	60	67.9	148.3	52.2	122.1	20:80	75	64.8	141.8	56.8	129.4
15	130			55.2	139.4	10:90	150	61.7	129.8	59.3	141.8

Permeation measured at 35 °C. 1 barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm/cm² s cmHg.

Table. S9. Temperature dependent (20-100 °C) single and mixed gas CO₂/CH₄ separation on 6FDA-DAM and (001)-A1FFIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM membrane.

Permeation temperature (°C)	Single gas				Mixed gas			
	CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity		CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity	
	PI	MMM	PI	MMM	PI	MMM	PI	MMM
20	919.6	1306.5	25.2	37.6	832.5	1206.7	26.1	45.3
35	881.9	1295.7	20.3	32.8	804.6	1198.0	21.1	40.4
55	809.6	1288.7	16.5	27.4	719.9	1215.4	17.8	34.3
75	687.8	1317.3	13.2	23.1	611.2	1278.2	13.8	29.8
100	487.7	1439.6	10.3	18.9	475.0	1423.5	10.1	26.1

Single gas: CO₂ feed pressure 15 psi, CH₄ feed pressure 60 psi. Mixed gas: CO₂/CH₄: 20/80 (v/v), feed pressure 75 psi.

Table. S10. Temperature dependent (20-100 °C) single and mixed gas CO₂/CH₄ separation on 6FDA-DAM-DAT and (001)-A1FFIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT membrane.

Permeation temperature (°C)	Single gas				Mixed gas			
	CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity		CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity	
	PI	MMM	PI	MMM	PI	MMM	PI	MMM
20	283.1	556.9	45.8	88.3	233.4	480.9	42.5	88.6
35	289.7	588.6	35.1	81.6	241.6	505.8	35.4	82.7
55	239.4	621.9	29.2	79.7	221.3	539.3	26.9	80.9
75	213.2	678.8	21.1	77.9	202.5	625.9	19.9	79.7
100	170.0	822.8	14.2	76.8	179.1	813.7	13.8	78.6

Single gas: CO₂ feed pressure 15 psi, CH₄ feed pressure 60 psi. Mixed gas: CO₂/CH₄: 20/80 (v/v), feed pressure 75 psi.

Table. S11. Temperature dependent (20-100 °C) single and mixed gas CO₂/CH₄ separation on 6FDA-DAT and (001)-A1FFIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT membrane.

Permeation temperature (°C)	Single gas				Mixed gas			
	CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity		CO ₂ Permeability (barrer)		CO ₂ /CH ₄ Selectivity	
	PI	MMM	PI	MMM	PI	MMM	PI	MMM
20	64.4	142.1	67.1	135.7	62.4	133.5	69.5	138.6
35	67.9	148.3	52.2	122.1	64.8	141.8	56.8	129.4
55	66.7	162.0	42.8	108.1	63.2	156.4	42.4	113.9
75	65.2	202.8	26.3	98.9	62.8	198.2	29.4	105.7
100	64.6	283.9	20.5	94.3	61.9	279.3	22.3	99.8

Single gas: CO₂ feed pressure 15 psi, CH₄ feed pressure 60 psi. Mixed gas: CO₂/CH₄: 20/80 (v/v), feed pressure 75 psi.

Table S12. Solubility and diffusivity of CO₂ and CH₄, and CO₂/CH₄ sorption selectivity and diffusion selectivity in (001)-AIFVIVE/6FDA-DAM-DAT and pure 6FDA-DAM-DAT membranes obtained temperature range of 20-100 °C.

Membranes	Temperature (°C)	Permeability (barrer)		Selectivity CO ₂ /CH ₄	Solubility (10 ⁻² cm ³ (STP)/cmHg/cm ³)		Diffusivity (10 ⁻⁸ cm ² /s)		Selectivity	
		CO ₂	CH ₄		CO ₂	CH ₄	CO ₂	CH ₄	Solubility CO ₂ /CH ₄	Diffusivity CO ₂ /CH ₄
6FDA-DAM-DAT	20	283.1	6.2	45.9	29.2	5.3	9.7	1.2	5.6	8.2
	35	289.6	8.3	35.1	23.5	4.0	12.3	2.1	5.8	6.0
	55	239.3	8.2	29.1	14.8	2.7	16.2	3.0	5.5	5.3
	75	213.2	10.1	21.1	9.8	1.9	21.8	5.3	5.1	4.1
	100	170.1	12.0	14.2	5.3	1.0	32.1	11.9	5.2	2.7
(001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	20	556.9	6.3	88.3	74.6	12.1	7.5	0.5	6.2	14.4
	35	588.6	7.2	81.6	54.2	9.8	10.9	0.7	5.6	14.7
	55	621.8	7.8	79.7	36.8	7.4	16.9	1.1	5.0	16.1
	75	678.5	8.7	77.9	26.3	5.5	25.8	1.6	4.8	16.3
	100	822.7	10.7	76.8	17.8	3.9	46.2	2.7	4.6	16.7

CO₂ feed pressure 15 psi, CH₄ feed pressure 60 psi.

Table S13. A comparison of single and mixed gas CO₂/CH₄ separation performances, and selectivity (*S*) and permeability (*P*) enhancement of MOFs/6FDA-polyimides MMMs with [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes developed in this study.

MOFs	Polymers	MOF (wt%)	Measurement condition			CO ₂ permeability (barrer)			CO ₂ /CH ₄ selectivity			Ref. ^ψ
			<i>P</i> (bar)	CO ₂ /CH ₄ ratio	<i>T</i> (°C)	polymer	MMM	<i>P</i> [#] (%)	polymer	MMM	<i>S</i> [§] (%)	
AIFVIVE-1-Ni ²⁺	6FDA-DAM	58.9	10.0	10/90	35	730.2	1095.4	50.0	20.6	41.2	100.2	<i>this work</i>
AIFVIVE-1-Ni ²⁺	6FDA-DAM-DAT	59.6	10.0	10/90	35	204.7	435.9	112.9	34.8	84.7	143.4	
AIFVIVE-1-Ni ²⁺	6FDA-DAT	60.3	10.0	10/90	35	61.7	129.8	110.4	59.3	141.8	139.1	
<i>Y-fum-fcu</i> -MOF	6FDA-DAM	30.1	1.4	100	35	716.9	1365.0	90.4	18.9	23.3	23.4	11
<i>Y-fum-fcu</i> -MOF	6FDA-DAM-DABA	17.7	1.4	SG	35	172.7	286.8	66.0	37.1	38.0	2.6	11
<i>Y-fum-fcu</i> -MOF	6FDA-DAM	20.0	1.4	SG	35	661.0	952.4	44.1	23.1	26.3	14.1	42
NbOFFIVE-1-Ni	6FDA-DAM	20.0	1.4	SG	35	744.8	954.3	28.1	18.5	20.9	12.9	38
NbOFFIVE-1-Ni	6FDA-DAM	20.0	6.9	50/50	35	721.3	1007.8	39.7	24.1	26.3	9.1	
ZIF-90	6FDA-DAM	15.0	2.0	SG	25	390.0	800.0	105.1	24.0	28.0	16.7	43
MOF-74	6FDA-Durene	21.0	1.0	50/50	35	843.4	2250.0	166.8	12.5	15.7	25.7	44
MOF-74	6FDA-DAM	23.0	1.0	50/50	35	843.4	1217.0	44.3	15.5	16.1	3.9	
MOF-74	6FDA-DAT	15.0	1.0	50/50	35	45.4	52.0	14.7	40.3	55.6	37.7	45
ZIF-8	6FDA-Durene	20.0	10.0	SG	35	352.0	487.0	38.4	16.6	17.9	8.0	
sod-ZMOF	6FDA-DAM	20.0	2.1	50/50	35	1062.3	1408.1	44.2	22.1	26.2	35.6	41

Single gas (SG), permeation temperature 35 °C. ²⁺(001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets, [#]Permeability enhancement factor, [§]Selectivity enhancement factor, 1 barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm/cm² s cmHg; 1 bar = 100 kPa. ^ψReferences in main text.

Table S14. A comparison of mixed gas CO₂/CH₄ separation performances, and selectivity (*S*) and permeability (*P*) enhancement of CuBDC and MIL-53-NH₂ nanosheets/polymers MMMs with [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes developed in this study.

MOFs	Polymers	Nano-sheets (wt%)	Measurement condition			CO ₂ permeability (barrer)			CO ₂ /CH ₄ selectivity			Ref. ^ψ
			<i>P</i> (bar)	CO ₂ /CH ₄ ratio	<i>T</i> (°C)	polymer	MMM	<i>P</i> [#] (%)	polymer	MMM	<i>S</i> [§] (%)	
AIFFIVE-1-Ni ²⁺	6FDA-DAM	58.9	10.0	10/90	35	730.2	1095.4	50.0	20.6	41.2	100.2	<i>this work</i>
AIFFIVE-1-Ni ²⁺	6FDA-DAM-DAT	59.6	10.0	10/90	35	204.7	435.9	112.9	34.8	84.7	143.4	
AIFFIVE-1-Ni ²⁺	6FDA-DAT	60.3	10.0	10/90	35	61.7	129.8	110.4	59.3	141.8	139.1	
Cu-BDC ^θ	Matrimid	8.2	3.0	50/50	35	5.8	4.1	-29.2	59.8	78.7	31.6	17
Cu-BDC ^θ	6FDA-DAM	4.0	1.0	50/50	25	590.0	430.0	-27.1	30.0	43.0	43.3	34
Cu-BDC ^θ	Matrimid	12.0	5.0	50/50	35	13.3	6.3	-52.6	25.1	38.0	51.4	35
NH ₂ -MIL-53(Al) ^β	Matrimid	8.0	3.0	50/50	35	6.8	13.3	95.6	30.5	31.1	2.0	18

²⁺(001)-AIFFIVE-1-Ni nanosheets, ^θCu-BDC nanosheets, ^βNH₂-MIL-53(Al) nanosheets. Permeation temperature 35 °C. [#]Permeability enhancement factor, [§]Selectivity enhancement factor, 1 barrer = 10⁻¹⁰ cm³ (STP) cm/cm² s cmHg; 1 bar = 100 kPa. ^ψReferences in main text.

Table S15. Overview of representative MOFs based mixed-matrix membranes for CO₂/CH₄ separation.

MOFs	Polymer	MOF loading (wt%)	Measurement conditions			CO ₂ permeability (barrer)	CO ₂ /CH ₄ selectivity	Ref.
			<i>P</i> (bar)	CO ₂ /CH ₄ ratio	<i>T</i> (°C)			
AIFFFIVE-1-Ni ²⁺	6FDA-DAM	58.9				1095.4	41.2	<i>this work</i>
	6FDA-DAM-DAT	59.6	10.0	10/90	35	435.9	84.7	
	6FDA-DAT	60.3				129.8	141.8	
Y- <i>fum</i> - <i>fcu</i> -MOF	6FDA-DAM	30.1				1365.0	23.3	11
	6FDA-DAM-DABA	17.7	1.4	single	35	286.8	38.0	42
	6FDA-DAM	20.0				952.4	26.3	
NbOFFIVE-1-Ni	6FDA-DAM	20.0	1.4	single	35	954.3	20.9	38
	6FDA-DAM	20.0	6.9	50/50		1007.8	26.3	
MOF-74	6FDA-Durene	21.0				2250.0	15.7	
	6FDA-DAM	23.0	1.0	50/50	35	1217.0	16.1	44
	6FDA-DAT	15.0				52.0	55.6	
	PIM-1	20.0	2.0		25	21269.0	19.0	77
UiO-66	6FDA-ODA	25.0	10.0	single	35	50.4	46.1	78
	6FDA-ODA	25.0	10.0	50/50		50.4	42.3	
	PIM-1	28.0	5.0	50/50	25	10900.0	13.0	79
UiO-66-NH ₂	6FDA-ODA	25.0	10.0	50/50	35	13.7	44.7	78
	PIM-1	20.0	4.0	single	25	2210.0	25.1	14
MIL-53	6FDA-DAM:HAB	15.0	10.0	single	35	71.1	15.1	80
	Matrimid®5218	15.0	3.0	single	25	12.4	51.8	81
	Ultem	15.0	10.0	50/50	35	1.8	42.8	82
	6FDA-ODA:DAM	20.0	10.0	50/50	35	61.5	13.0	
MIL-53-NH ₂	6FDA-DAM:HAB	20.0	10.0	pure	35	44.3	27.7	80
	PSF	30.0	3.0	50/50	30	40.0	29.2	83
	Matrimid®5218	16.0	3.0	50/50	25	7.4	42.0	13
	6FDA-DAM	20.0	2.0	50/50	25	680.0	27.9	
	Matrimid®9725	30.0	9.0	50/50	35	50.0	37.0	84
	Ultem	15.0	10.0	50/50	35	3.0	36.1	82
	6FDA-ODA:DAM	15.0	10.0	50/50	25	113.0	28.5	
sod-ZMOF	Matrimid®5218	20.0	4.0	50/50	35	13.8	43.4	85
	6FDA-DAM	20.0	2.1	50/50	35	1408.4	26.2	41
ZIF-7	Pebax	34.0	3.8	single	20	41.0	44.0	86
ZIF-8	PSF	5.0	4.0	single	27	3.2	28.5	87
	Matrimid®5218	30.0	5.0	50/50	35	25.0	53.0	88
	Matrimid®5218	50.0	2.7	single	25	4.7	124.9	89
	PIM-1	43.0	1.0	single	22	6300.0	14.7	90
	6FDA-Durene	50.0	3.5	single	35	1552.9	11.0	91
	6FDA-Durene	41.9	10.0	single	35	779.0	20.9	45
ZIF-71	6FDA-Durene	20.0	3.5	50/50	35	3435.0	16.0	92
ZIF-90	Matrimid	15.0	2.0	single	25	10.5	35.0	43
	6FDA-DAM	15.0	2.0	single	25	800.0	28.0	

Continue

MOFs	Polymer	MOF loading (wt%)	Measurement conditions			CO ₂ permeability (barrer)	CO ₂ /CH ₄ selectivity	Ref.
			P (bar)	CO ₂ /CH ₄ ratio	T (°C)			
HKUST-1	Matrimid®5218	30.0	10.0	50/50	25	14.0	46.0	93
	PVDF	15.0	5.0	single	25	3.2	40.1	94
	ODPA-TMPDA	20.0	2.0	single	35	142.5	28.0	95
	6FDA-ODA	25.0	10.0	single	35	21.8	51.2	78
MOF-5	PEI	25.0	6.0	single	25	5.4	23.4	96
	Matrimid®5218	30.0	2.0	single	35	20.2	44.7	97
MIL-101	PSF	24.0	2.0	50/50	35	18.0	28.0	98
MIL-101-NH ₂	PSF	25.0	3.0	50/50	35	5.4	27.0	99

[‡](001)-AIFVIVE-1-Ni nanosheets.

Table. S16. A comparison of mixed gas H₂S/CO₂/CH₄ separation performances, and selectivity (S) and permeability (P) enhancement of MOFs/6FDA-polyimides MMMs with [001]-oriented MMMOF membranes.

Membrane	Gas mixture (H ₂ S:CO ₂ :CH ₄)	Permeability (barrer)				Selectivity		Enh [#] (%)		Ref.
		H ₂ S	CO ₂	H ₂ S+CO ₂	H ₂ S/CH ₄	CO ₂ /CH ₄	(H ₂ S+CO ₂)/CH ₄	P	S	
6FDA-DAM		514.7	693.3	1208.0	18.7	25.2	43.9	--	--	
(001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM	1/9/90 ^a	961.1	1008.9	1970.0	47.7	50.1	97.8	63.1	123	
6FDA-DAM		523.9	732.0	1255.9	19.0	26.5	45.5	--	--	
(001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM	2/18/80 ^b	979.9	1060.4	2040.3	45.9	49.6	99.4	62.5	118	
6FDA-DAM		350.2	769.1	1119.3	14.5	31.7	46.2	--	--	
(001)-AIFVIVE(58.9)/6FDA-DAM	5/5/90 ^a	573.0	944.9	1517.9	39.0	64.2	103.2	35.6	123	
6FDA-DAM-DAT		82.0	202.7	284.7	18.5	45.7	64.1	--	--	
(001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	1/9/90 ^a	221.9	358.6	580.5	51.8	83.8	135.6	103.9	112	
6FDA-DAM-DAT		82.7	210.4	293.1	18.8	47.7	66.5	--	--	This work
(001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	2/18/80 ^b	246.5	393.7	640.2	56.2	89.7	145.8	118.4	119	
6FDA-DAM-DAT		64.9	196.9	261.8	16.9	51.3	68.2	--	--	
(001)-AIFVIVE(59.6)/6FDA-DAM-DAT	5/5/90 ^a	140.6	305.5	446.1	45.3	98.4	143.7	70.4	111	
6FDA-DAT		12.3	53.4	65.7	16.7	72.7	89.3	--	--	
(001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT	1/9/90 ^a	39.2	118.5	157.7	45.1	136.3	181.4	140.1	103	
6FDA-DAT		12.7	56.7	69.4	17.1	76.3	93.4	--	--	
(001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT	2/18/80 ^b	42.1	124.2	166.3	48.9	144.3	193.2	139.5	107	
6FDA-DAT		10.6	53.1	63.7	15.2	76.4	91.6	--	--	
(001)-AIFVIVE(60.3)/6FDA-DAT	5/5/90 ^a	29.3	107.1	136.3	40.7	149.0	189.7	114.0	107	
6FDA-DAM		258.2	413.5	671.7	15.3	24.4	39.7	--	--	
Y-fum-fcu-MOF(30)/6FDA-DAM	20/20/60 ^c	469.8	587.9	1057.7	23.4	29.3	52.7	57.5	33	11
6FDA-DAM-DABA		42.4	95.6	138.0	16.4	36.1	52.5			
Y-fum-fcu-MOF(17.7)/6FDA-DAM-DABA		67.3	158.6	225.9	19.7	46.4	66.1	63.7	26	
NbOFFIVE-1-Ni(20)/6FDA-DAM	20/20/60 ^c	401.0	547.0	948.0	20.7	28.2	48.9	41.1	23	38
6FDA-DAM		167.0	137.0	304.0	7.3	9.1	16.4			
UiO-66-NH-COCH ₃ (16)/6FDA-DAM	30/5/65 ^d	193.0	172.0	365.0	16.2	18.2	34.4	20.1	109	39

Feed pressure: ^a 10 bar; ^b 5 bar; ^c 6.9 bar; ^d 20 bar. All permeation measured at 35 °C. Enh[#] enhancement.

Table S17. Lattice parameters of the DFT-optimized and experimental AIFVIVE-1-Ni bulk structure.

Structural model	a [Å]	b [Å]	c [Å]	α [°]	β [°]	γ [°]	Volume [Å ³]
This work	9.785	9.785	15.446	90	90	90	1479.06
<i>Exp.</i> (25)	9.876	9.876	15.120	90	90	90	1474.81

Table S18. 12-6 LJ parameters and DDEC partial charges ascribed to the atoms of the AIFVIVE-1-Ni (001) surface structure.

Atom type	ϵ_{ii} [kcal/mol]	σ_{ii} [Å]	Q_i [e]
Al	0.505	4.008	+1.661
Ni	0.015	2.525	+0.735
C	0.095	3.473	+0.062
H	0.015	2.847	+0.135
N	0.077	3.262	-0.236
F1	0.050	2.997	-0.604
F2	0.050	2.997	-0.623
F3	0.050	2.997	-0.561

Table S19. Lattice parameters and representative geometric features - bond distances (L) and valence angles (A) - of the DFT- and force field NPT MD-generated AIFVIVE-1-Ni surface slab models.

Lattice parameters	Structure model		Geometric features	Structure model	
	<i>DFT</i>	<i>NPT MD</i>		<i>DFT</i>	<i>NPT MD</i>
a [Å]	9.785	9.742	L_{Ni-N}	2.07	2.13
b [Å]	9.785	9.742	L_{Ni-F2}	2.01	1.94
z [Å]	42.57	41.41	L_{Al-F2}	1.85	1.81
α [°]	90	90	$A_{Al-F-Ni}$	177.5	176.3
β [°]	90	90	A_{N-Ni-N}	179.0	177.6
γ [°]	90	90	A_{F-Ni-N}	89.4	89.9

Table S20. 12-6 LJ parameters and atomic charges for the 6FDA-DAM model.

Atom type	Number	ϵ_{ii} [kcal/mol]	σ_{ii} [Å]	Q_i [e]
CA11	1,11	0.0417	3.88	-0.137
CA12	6,12			-0.023
CA21	2,10			+0.082
CA22	3,9			-0.049
CA23	5,13			-0.039
CA24	28	0.0417	3.88	-0.350
CA3	4,8			+0.305
CA4	26,30			-0.425
CA5	27,29,31			+0.470
CH0	7			0.0010
CF3	14,15	0.0417	4.73	+0.053
CH3	32,33,34	0.1947	3.75	-0.080
COO	16,18,21,23	0.1689	3.72	+0.369
OCO	19,20,24,25	0.3924	3.05	-0.383
NN1	17,22	0.0238	3.78	+0.107
OES	Termination	0.1093	2.80	-0.102
NA1	Termination	0.2206	3.34	-0.660
HA1	Termination	0.0000	0.00	+0.330

Movie S1.

The dispersion of nanoparticles and nanosheets: The nanosheets express a different reflection index.

Movie S2.

The in-plane arrangement of (001)-nanosheets within the polymer matrix. The video was constructed from 430 sliced images to cover an extensive area ($15 \times 15 \mu^2$) of the [001]-oriented MMMOF membrane.